

**Balancing Compliance and Innovation: Addressing Explainability in AI Systems under
the EU AI Act**

by

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Table of contents

1	Introduction	7
1.1	Foundational terminology	7
1.2	Research questions and methodology	10
1.3	The benefits of explainability.....	13
1.4	Thesis structure	14
2	Explainability in the normative context	16
2.1	The AI Act and its context	16
2.1.1	The genesis of the EU AI Act	17
2.1.2	Scope of the AI Act.....	21
2.1.3	High-risk AI Systems	24
2.1.4	Requirements of high-risk systems: Is there an explainability obligation?	26
2.1.5	Oversight: How will compliance be checked?.....	28
2.2	The global normative context.....	29
2.2.1	International level approaches.....	29
2.2.2	National level approaches	30
2.2.3	Approaches of standard-setting organizations	32
2.3	Closing the chapter on legal aspects of explainability	34
3	Explainability in the technological context	35
3.1	Basing AI Systems on intrinsically interpretable models	36
3.1.1	Assessing interpretability	37
3.1.2	The accuracy-interpretability trade-off debate	39
3.1.3	Other potential downsides of interpretable models.....	40
3.1.4	Overview of main white box models	40
3.2	Using XAI tools to explain black box models	50
3.2.1	Weaknesses of XAI techniques.....	51
3.2.2	Classifying XAI techniques	52

3.2.1	Benchmarks for explainability	53
3.2.2	Global explanation approaches	53
3.2.3	Local explanation approaches	59
3.3	Closing the chapter on explainability in a technological context.....	70
4	Explainability in the organizational context.....	71
4.1	Defining and evaluating explanations	71
4.1.1	Navigating trade-offs: When to use which approach?	71
4.1.2	Human-centered benchmarks and principles for explainability.....	72
4.1.3	The Role of Stakeholders in Shaping Explainability: From Theory to Standardization.....	73
4.1.4	Choosing the right elements of an explanation	74
4.1.5	Designing and evaluating explanation interfaces.....	75
4.2	Resource constraints, governance, and regulatory risk	78
4.2.1	Human resources constraints.....	78
4.2.2	Computational capabilities constraints.....	79
4.2.3	Managerial and governance challenges.....	80
4.2.4	Legal and liability risks	81
5	The strategic context: The competitiveness and innovation trade-offs.....	82
6	Framework for implementing explainability.....	85
7	Conclusion.....	91
	Bibliography	93

List of figures

Figure 1. Annual number of publications on Explainable Artificial Intelligence, 2008–2024.....	9
Figure 2. Conceptual map of chapters feeding into the Framework.....	15
Figure 3. Timeline of key milestones leading to the adoption and phased implementation of the AI Act.....	17
Figure 4. Structure of the HLEG Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI.....	18
Figure 5. Overview of high-risk AI systems under the EU AI Act.....	25
Figure 6. The interpretability–complexity continuum of common machine learning models.....	39
Figure 7. Top Features Table by absolute weight for a global interpretation of a logistic regression model.....	41
Figure 8. Formula for interpreting logistic regression coefficients in terms of odds ratios.....	42
Figure 9. Plots for local interpretation of a decision made by a logistic regression model.....	42
Figure 10. Generalized Additive Model (GAM) structure.....	43
Figure 11. Global feature importance plot for a decision tree model.....	44
Figure 12. Local feature attribution for a single prediction made by a decision tree model.....	45
Figure 13. Example of a local explanation generated by a RIPPER-based rule model.....	48
Figure 14. Comparison between a standard model and a Concept Bottleneck Model.....	49
Figure 15. Visual explanation generated by ProtoPNet.....	50
Figure 16. Explainable machine learning pipeline.....	51
Figure 17. Partial Dependence Plots that illustrate the marginal effect of a continuous and a binary feature.....	54
Figure 18. An Accumulated Local Effects Plot.....	56
Figure 19. Top 5 features ranked by Permutation Feature Importance across three runs on a black box model.....	57
Figure 20. Top 5 features identified by a decision tree surrogate model.....	58
Figure 21. LIME optimization formula.....	60
Figure 22. LIME stability test for one instance.....	61
Figure 23. Effect of LIME sample size and kernel width on explanation stability and runtime.....	62
Figure 24. Illustration of the LIME process for explaining image classification.....	63
Figure 25. The top 8 features that contribute most to a prediction for one instance, based on SHAP values.....	66
Figure 26. SHAP force plot for local explanations.....	67
Figure 27. SHAP values across five explanation runs for the same instance.....	67
Figure 28. SHAP summary plot showing the top 10 features influencing model predictions globally.....	68
Figure 29. Explanation styles in AI systems, as defined by NISTIR 8312.....	75
Figure 30. The Framework for implementing explainability in high-risk AI Systems under the AI Act.....	90

List of tables

Table 1. Framework for implementing explainability in high-risk AI Systems.....	86
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Abstract

The European Union's Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act) has sparked debate over its compliance burdens, legal ambiguities, and potential impact on the EU's global competitiveness and innovation capacity. Central to these debates is the requirement to understand both the general functioning and specific outputs of black-box models in high-risk contexts, an issue addressed within the field of explainable artificial intelligence (XAI). While the AI Act imposes binding obligations and stiff penalties, it remains unclear how organizations can operationalize these requirements in practice. This thesis addresses that gap by integrating insights from three domains: i) legal and ethical expectations from the AI Act and relevant standards, ii) technical strategies for meeting these expectations through interpretable models and post-hoc XAI techniques, and iii) organizational challenges in implementing such solutions under real-world constraints. The research adopts a non-systematic integrative literature review, semi-structured expert interviews, and a mixed-method exploration. Three main contributions emerge from this thesis. First, it introduces a typology of explainability use cases, mandatory interpretability, strict explainability, and balanced explainability, tailored to context-dependent reliability demand for explanation methods. Second, it reveals that the AI Act's explainability requirements are unlikely to hinder the EU's innovation or global competitiveness significantly, given the broad acceptance of the need for explainability in governance frameworks across the globe, coupled with the growing market demand for explainability. Finally, the thesis proposes a practical implementation framework to help providers of high-risk AI systems meet the AI Act's explainability standards while maintaining competitiveness and managing regulatory uncertainty.

List of key abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence.
AI Act	Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act).
AI System	As defined by Article 3, paragraph 1 of the AI Act. See more in Subsection 2.1.2.1.
EU	The European Union
February 2025 Guidelines	Commission Guidelines on the definition of an artificial intelligence system established by Regulation (EU) 2024/1689.
GDPR	Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).
HLEG Guidelines	The Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI of the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence.
XAI	The research field and its techniques that aim to make black models explainable.

1 Introduction

In recent years, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has captured public attention for its transformative potential as well as its risks [1]. This has triggered a shift from regulation by soft-law instruments (such as ethical codes and standards) towards a binding regulatory framework [2]. The European Union is so far the only jurisdiction that has enacted a general and comprehensive regulation on AI, known as the AI Act, as presented in the Subchapter 2.2. However, the AI Act has sparked a strong backlash, so intense that at the time of this writing, there are serious talks of watering down or scrapping the AI Act altogether [3].

One general concern is that the AI Act will negatively impact the EU's competitiveness and innovativeness [4]. The fears are exacerbated by the unprecedentedly high penalties and the ambiguities about the application of the AI Act in practice [5]. As this thesis will show, one such point is the explainability standards for high-risk AI Systems imposed by the AI Act. Therefore, this thesis aims to develop a framework that organizations can use to recognize and tackle the legal, technical, and organizational challenges of implementing explainability standards in the context of the AI Act, with the primary objective of relaxing negative pressures on competitiveness and innovativeness.

1.1 Foundational terminology

Let's start with the driving force behind this thesis: the black box. This term refers to a machine learning model whose internal logic and decision-making processes are not comprehensible to humans without the application of additional techniques [6]. The *opacity* of black boxes usually arises from technical characteristics, such as: **i)** architectural complexity; **ii)** non-linear functions; **iii)** large numbers of parameters; **iv)** the nature and structure of data; **v)** adaptive behaviors that change over time [2], [7], [8], [9]. Sometimes, however, opacity is *intentionally introduced* under the rationale of proprietary information – a practice criticized for precluding meaningful scrutiny, thus disincentivizing careful design [8], [10]. In other cases, opaqueness is *unintentionally introduced*, for example, due to poor documentation management [2], [8].

For this thesis, "*black box models*" refers exclusively to machine learning models that are inherently opaque due to their architectural complexity or the nature of the data they process. This is partly due to scope limitations, but also because the AI Act's transparency and documentation obligations aim to eliminate black box models that result from intentional or

unintentional human actions or omissions. By contrast, this thesis will use the term “*white box models*” to refer to models whose logic, structure, and decision-making processes are directly accessible and understandable to humans, without requiring the application of additional techniques to extract information.

The rise in *explainability* emerges in the context of humanity’s increasing use of black box models for consequential decisions, such as healthcare, justice, or security. Without understanding the black box, individuals and societies cannot participate in decision making, thus facing the “*threat of algocracy*” [8]. Lack of understanding also impacts AI adoption negatively, because without understanding black boxes, trust in AI will remain elusive, especially in sensitive domains [8]. From this, it naturally follows that comprehending the output of a black box is as important as its accuracy; we must know that AI is acting “*in the right way (how) and for the right reasons (why)*” [8]. The field of *explainable AI (XAI)* emerges to find ways to solve the *black box problem*, providing techniques that elucidate the functioning and decision-making of black box models [2], [7], [11].

There are many challenges related to explainability, not least of which is defining what it means. There is considerable confusion between *explainability* and the related concepts of *interpretability* and *transparency*. Literature reveals that these terms often overlap, are used interchangeably, contradict each other, or are used as synonyms, undermining conceptual clarity essential for practical application [11], [12], [13], [14], [15]. This is understandable in a developing field, but more recent literature shows a trend toward clearer and more consistent use of these terms. The following paragraphs set out the definitions of these terms as they will be used in this thesis.

The literature review reveals that *interpretability* is defined in different ways or from various standpoints. Two main definitions can be summarized. The first one is the subjective definition [13]. This definition treats interpretability as the degree to which a model “makes sense” to a human. It emphasizes the subjective nature of interpretation, noting that factors such as human background, education, and perspective can influence what is considered interpretable. The other one is the objective definition. It links interpretability to models built using transparent functions (linear models or decision trees), where humans can grasp inputs, weights, and rules [7]. This thesis will use the objective definition and treat interpretability as the characteristic of a model to be understood by humans without applying explainability techniques.

In contrast, this thesis defines *explainability* as the ability to extract information about a black box model when its decisions are not interpretable. As answers cannot be gained simply by looking at the model, explainability necessitates applying additional post-training (*post hoc*) techniques that are decoupled from the model [7], [11], [13], [16], [17]. Explainability should be distinguished from XAI, which is the research field and its techniques that aim to make black models explainable [17], i.e., to realize explainability. However, defining XAI as a coherent discipline or formal technical concept is somewhat misleading, because the whole field is more like a movement or a collective effort [15].

To give a bit more context, understanding information-based systems was a topic before the dawn of data science, with knowledge-based expert systems in the 1980s [15]. Both Xu et al. and Rudin et al. have stated that *interpretable machine learning* has its roots dating back to the 1950s [18]. On the other hand, the ascent of XAI is located at the turn of the century. Meske et al. [15] listed the year 2002 as the moment when the term XAI was first used, coinciding with the rise of new-paradigm intelligent systems, like artificial neural networks. This recent but growing interest is demonstrated in the publication data. Figure 1 shows a sharp rise in academic interest in XAI in recent years, corresponding with the growing use and scrutiny of black-box machine learning models.

Figure 1. Annual number of publications on Explainable Artificial Intelligence, 2008–2024.

This chart illustrates the growing academic interest in XAI over the last decade and a half, as measured by the number of scholarly publications indexed each year. The data was obtained from OpenAlex, an open catalog of academic works [19].

Despite the acceptance of objective definitions of interpretability and explainability, this thesis acknowledges that explanation artifacts should be made as useful as possible to individuals with

different needs and within various contexts. That is why the study of both interpretability and explainability lies at the intersection of three major scientific domains: **i)** data science or AI - central to both the underlying prediction models and the explanation techniques; **ii)** human sciences - essential for understanding how humans process explanations; and **iii)** Human-Computer Interaction - key for creating interactive systems that are accessible and usable to the intended stakeholder [20].

This section on terminology would not be complete without introducing the concepts of *local* and *global* explanations [21]. Local explanations aim to clarify individual predictions by showing how specific inputs influenced a particular output. In contrast, global explanations offer insight into the overall logic and behavior of the model across the dataset. Both types of explanations are relevant in the context of inherently interpretable models and post-hoc explainability techniques. However, while white-box models provide both local and global explanations by design, XAI techniques typically specialize in one type.

Finally, *transparency* is a more general category than interpretability and explainability and covers the need for “*information about the entire life cycle of an AI system and its ecosystem*” [22] to be readily accessible to the relevant stakeholders, as stated by O. Müller et al. They clarify that transparency encompasses data sources, processing logic, modeling techniques, intended use, risk assessment, and other relevant factors. As interpretability and explainability are needed for some, although not all, aspects of transparency, it could be said that interpretability and explainability are part of the broader toolbox of transparency.

1.2 Research questions and methodology

To address the issues outlined in the introduction, this thesis is guided by one general research question and three specific sub-questions that structure the analytical approach.

General research question: *What are the essential traits and core components of a practical framework for explainability in high-risk AI systems, ensuring compliance with the EU AI Act while preserving performance and fostering innovation?*

Specific research questions:

1. *What are the key requirements of the AI Act in terms of explainability of black box models and their decisions?*

2. *What are the key operational and technical challenges in implementing explainability for high-risk AI systems under the AI Act?*
3. *What trade-offs exist between implementing explicability and maintaining performance and innovation potential?*

To answer these questions, three primary methods are employed.

The dominant method employed in this thesis is a **non-systematic integrative literature review**, conducted in line with the framework proposed by Kraus et al. [23]. This framework has four main elements:

- i) **Type** - The thesis adopts a *non-systematic literature review* approach. This choice reflects the goal-oriented nature of the research, which seeks to integrate relevant knowledge through the critical judgment informed by prior exposure, expertise, and experience, rather than through a formalized or replicable review protocol. The purpose is not to exhaustively survey all existing literature but to selectively analyze key contributions that support the development of actionable guidance for developers, legal experts, and decision-makers.
- ii) **Focus** - The review is a *between-domain hybrid*, as it synthesizes insights from multiple intersecting areas: AI regulation, techniques for developing interpretable or explainable models, and organizational implementation challenges. Chapter 3 adopts a method-focused perspective, systematically reviewing key methods for developing interpretable models and applying XAI techniques to black-box models.
- iii) **Method** - The review applies a *qualitative content analysis approach*, organizing and interpreting a curated body of literature based on thematic relevance. Only a sufficient number of sources are reviewed to enable the formulation of the proposed compliance framework. This reflects the thesis's goal-oriented design and emphasis on conceptual depth rather than breadth.
- iv) **Contribution** - The principal contribution of this literature review is to propose a practical and adaptable framework that supports organizations in achieving compliance with explainability requirements under the AI Act. Given that many of the technical and organizational challenges addressed are not unique to the EU context, the resulting guidance is likely to have broader applicability beyond the European regulatory environment.

In addition, the research employs **semi-structured in-depth individual interviews** with two industry experts: **i)** a senior healthcare IT expert in an established company offering radiology and hospital management systems used across clinical institutions, currently spearheading its AI experimentation efforts (Interviewee 1); **ii)** a co-founder of a leading Southeast European data science consultancy (Interviewee 2). The interviews were conducted following the methodology proposed by DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree [24]. According to this methodology, semi-structured interviews are a widely used qualitative research method and can be conducted either with individuals or in groups. Individual interviews were selected over group formats because they allow for a deeper exploration of participants' personal experiences, even if this may limit the diversity of perspectives. The semi-structured format was chosen for its balance between flexibility and comparability: it allows the interviewer to adapt questions in real time to elicit richer insights, while maintaining a consistent core structure across interviews to enable meaningful comparison. According to DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, the interview process typically begins with general questions to establish rapport, followed by more active probing to clarify and deepen understanding. While the methodology favors audio/video recording over notetaking, the latter was selected for this thesis. This choice was based on the interviewer's assessment that recording might create an artificial environment, leading participants to withhold information. For data extraction, two complementary approaches were used: **i)** identifying common patterns across the interviews, and **ii)** applying the immersion approach, whereby the researcher engages deeply with the interview text to allow insights to emerge intuitively. The complete list of guiding questions used during the semi-structured interviews is provided in Annex 1. The interviews provided valuable insights, focusing exclusively on the organizational challenges within the context of XAI.

A **mixed-method exploration experiment** was conducted to evaluate the application and outputs of various interpretability and explainability techniques. The experiment design drew upon the methodological recommendations for empirical software engineering studies proposed by Felderer and Travassons [25], and was further informed by insights on exploratory and descriptive case study designs provided by Baxter and Jack [26]. The experiment was performed on the structured University of California, Irvine (UCI) Heart Disease dataset, which was augmented with synthetic data to facilitate the training of a black-box neural network. For the assessment of interpretability techniques, several inherently interpretable models were constructed. In contrast, explainability techniques were tested exclusively on a single black-box model to evaluate their post-hoc explanatory power. All coding experiments were executed

in Google Colab, a cloud-based Python development environment, while the synthetic dataset was generated separately using R on a local machine. Full implementation details, including the R code for data generation and the Python scripts for model training and explanation, are available at: <https://github.com/VladimirBoshnjakovski/explainable-ai-thesis-code>. The aim of this study is twofold. First, to *systematically demonstrate the types of insights that different interpretability and explainability techniques produce* when applied to a structured dataset. Second, to *investigate and reflect on the practical challenges encountered during implementation*, such as interpretability–performance trade-offs, computational constraints, and the technical complexity of deploying various XAI methods. This empirical study combines exploratory data analysis with practical implementation, reflecting both qualitative and quantitative dimensions.

1.3 The benefits of explainability

Although this thesis focuses on the legal dimensions of explainability, the broader benefits of explainability as emphasized in the literature:

- **Avoiding bias and fairness issues** [2], [27], [28], [29], [30], [15]: Explainability is critical for detecting and addressing deeper, structural biases in model architecture. This is especially crucial in high-stakes domains such as criminal justice, healthcare, and employment.
- **Compliance with rules** [2], [27], [31], [32], [33]: Even in the absence of AI-specific regulation, existing laws often mandate particular processes or prohibit specific outcomes, particularly in domains like finance, healthcare, justice, and data privacy. Many legal systems, through constitutional and human rights documents, treat the right to a proper explanation as a fundamental safeguard of procedural fairness.
- **Establish accountability** [2], [34], [31], [35], [36]: In traditional hard-coded software, errors can be traced down to the smallest detail, albeit with considerable effort. In contrast, this is extremely difficult, if not impossible, in black box models. This encumbers “*a plaintiff or a regulator to establish, or to ascertain or to verify [responsibility]*” [36]. In this context, the concept of *contestability* is emerging, requiring that AI outputs be produced in a way that enables decisions made by automated systems to be challenged [37].

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- **Facilitating adoption** [2], [11], [29], [31], [35]: To foster trust, AI decisions and processes must be explainable both directly and indirectly to affected individuals. Without such understanding, the public will not trust these systems, and humans will naturally be hesitant to adopt tools that they do not understand. As a result, explainability is crucial for fostering usability and acceptance.
 - **Enhancing security** [34], [27], [29], [32], [14], [15]: Opaque AI systems make it difficult to assess security risks and adapt over time as they evolve. One such threat is adversarial attacks: small input manipulations that distort outputs, harder to detect and counter. XAI helps combat these threats. It also enhances system security by facilitating easier debugging, monitoring, and governance, while helping to address issues such as overfitting or data leakage through clearer model insights.
 - **Enhancing robustness** [34], [34], [27], [32], [15]: Even in the absence of malicious attacks, training data can shift over time, affecting a model's performance and trustworthiness in unpredictable ways. Understanding the reactions of models is crucial for enabling corrective action when outputs are flawed or harmful, anticipating vulnerabilities and implementing safeguards, and tracking errors to improve performance.
 - **Reputational benefits** [27]: Due to the high profile of the explainability issue, companies are trying to implement AI solutions to boost their reputation.
 - **Understanding of cause and effect** [14], [30], [15], [38]: Very often, machine learning is used not only for predictions, but for scientific exploration. In that case, we cannot extract knowledge without understanding how the used model made its predictions.

1.4 Thesis structure

This thesis is structured into six main chapters. The core contribution is developed in Chapters 2, 3 and 4 which lay the foundation for the framework for implementing explainability in high-risk AI systems under the AI Act. This framework is presented in Chapter 6. Chapter 5 provides the strategic context in which the framework would be implemented, while also assessing the impact of explainability obligations on competitiveness and innovativeness. The relationships between the chapters are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Conceptual map of chapters feeding into the Framework.

It illustrates how the chapters on the Normative Context, Technological Context, and Organizational Context, along with their subchapters, serve as foundational inputs into the development of the Explainability Compliance Framework in Chapter 6. Chapter 5 provides strategic context by framing the competitiveness and innovation challenges surrounding explainability compliance.

Chapter 0: Introduction presents the research topic by defining core concepts such as artificial intelligence, explainability, and transparency. It also discusses the broader significance of explainability beyond mere legal or ethical compliance. In addition, this chapter sets out the research questions and explains the methodological approach used to address them.

Chapter 2: Explainability in the normative context has two main parts. Subchapter 2.1 focuses on the AI Act, examining its legislative evolution, definitions, roles, and oversight. Section 2.1.4 plays a pivotal role by identifying the specific provisions within the AI Act that make explainability indispensable for achieving compliance. Subchapter 2.2 examines how explainability is addressed globally in ethical codes, standards, policy, and legislation. It contextualizes the AI Act and assesses competitiveness pressures from regulatory divergence.

Chapter 3: Explainability in the technological context turns to the technical dimensions of explainability and is divided into two parts. Chapter 3.1 addresses inherently interpretable models, while Subchapter 3.1 examines post hoc explanation tools used for black-box models. Both technical strands discuss the relevant strengths, weaknesses, and metrics of the covered techniques. Findings and visualizations from the thesis experiment are also included to highlight the key characteristics and explanation artifacts of the examined techniques.

Chapter 4: Explainability in the organizational context shifts to the organizational challenges of operationalizing the approaches discussed in Chapter 3. It explores how organizations navigate decisions on which explanation techniques to adopt, how they assess and benchmark the quality of explanations from a human understandability aspect, and the limitations they face, including resource constraints, governance barriers, legal liability concerns, and computational demands. The chapter also proposes practical strategies to mitigate the impacts of the identified challenges.

Chapter 5: The Strategic Context: Competitiveness and Innovation Trade-Offs examines whether the explainability requirements of the AI Act may negatively impact the EU's competitiveness and innovation capacity. This analysis considers the general correlation between regulation and innovation, the regulatory and ethical discrepancies between the EU and other global jurisdictions discussed in Chapter 2, as well as evolving market demands and trends. By addressing these competitiveness-compliance trade-offs, the thesis situates the proposed framework within the strategic and economic context in which organizations operate.

Finally, **Chapter 6: Framework for implementing explainability in high-risk AI Systems in the context of the AI Act** presents the proposed framework by outlining its key components, implementation phases, and integration steps. The framework should serve as a roadmap to help providers of high-risk AI Systems achieve compliance with the AI Act while minimizing negative impacts on competitiveness.

2 Explainability in the normative context

This chapter examines the legal, ethical, and policy frameworks that shape the requirements and expectations for explainability in AI systems. It situates the EU AI Act within the broader global landscape of legislative initiatives, ethical guidelines, and standardization efforts.

2.1 The AI Act and its context

This subchapter outlines the evolution of the EU's legislative and ethical approach to artificial intelligence, with a focus on explainability as a cornerstone of trustworthy AI. It traces the development from early policy initiatives and ethical guidelines to the binding provisions of the AI Act, highlighting how transparency, explicability, and accountability have become central legal obligations in the EU's AI governance framework.

2.1.1 The genesis of the EU AI Act

The legislative journey that culminated in the enactment of the AI Act, depicted in Figure 3, began in February 2017, when the European Parliament adopted its *Resolution with recommendations to the Commission on Civil Law Rules on Robotics* [39]. The Resolution demonstrates the early acknowledgment of AI’s potential to undermine due process, transparency, and comprehensibility in decision-making. It also emphasized the need for AI decisions that substantially impact individuals to be accompanied by a human-comprehensible rationale. The next big step was the *European Council in October 2017*, which called for a “*future-oriented regulatory framework*” [40] and directed the Commission to propose a text by early 2018.

Figure 3. Timeline of key milestones leading to the adoption and phased implementation of the AI Act.

Timeline of key milestones leading to the adoption and phased implementation of the AI Act. The figure illustrates the Act’s gradual development from 2017 onward through major institutional steps. Although formally enacted in July 2024, the Act will continue to evolve through guidelines, standards, and practical interpretations by institutions and courts.

The Commission responded to the Council's call with its *Communication on Artificial Intelligence for Europe* [41], issued in April 2018. This document launched a European AI initiative aimed at: **i)** enhancing technological and industrial capacity; **ii)** preparing for socio-

economic changes; and **iii**) ensuring an appropriate ethical and legal framework based on the core values of the EU. Transparency and explainability are central themes of this document, both in acknowledging the right to meaningful information on the logic used in automated decisions, which is already established in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and in calling for research into explainability. Finally, this document called for the drafting of AI ethics guidelines aligned with the Charter of Fundamental Rights.

These guidelines came in the form of the *Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI* (HLEG Guidelines) [31], published in April 2019. It was prepared by the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (HLEG), a group composed of 52 experts from academia, civil society, and industry. It represents a watershed moment in the

s approach to AI governance and embodies a key tool for interpreting the AI Act [42]. The main elements of the HLEG Guidelines are presented in Figure 4. At the highest level, the component of trustworthy AI systems is that they are lawful, ethical, and robust. The first two are key for this thesis.

Figure 4. Structure of the HLEG Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI.

The figure outlines the three core elements of trustworthy AI: lawfulness, ethics, and robustness. The ethics component is supported by four key ethical values, including explicability. In turn, the ethical values are operationalized via seven requirements, with the *transparency* requirement encompassing explainability, traceability, and communication.

Firstly, lawful means that even in the absence of AI-specific laws, existing regulations apply to AI, highlighting the need to respect existing rules that mandate explanations. Based on this

stipulation of the HLEG Guidelines, this thesis takes the position that even without the existence of the AI Act, AI does not function in a legal vacuum or without any regard to the EU's fundamental values. Take the Charter of Fundamental Rights that guarantees the right to give informed consent in the field of medicine (Article 3) and the right to an effective remedy (Article 47) [43]. It would be impossible to provide these rights if an AI System makes a decision or recommendation without giving a reliable explanation. On a regulatory level, questions regarding explainability predate the AI Act. Scholars have been discussing the right to information in the context of automatic decision-making under Articles 13 and 22 of the GDPR [44], including which XAI techniques satisfy its standards [11], [28], [30], [33], [45]. Finally, many ethical codes and industry standards necessitate that decisions be explainable to both practitioners and subjects. For example, Article 5 of the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine (Oviedo Convention) [46] stipulates that patients should be given appropriate information as to the purpose and nature of the intervention, its consequences, and its risks.

Secondly, regarding the ethics component, the HLEG Guidelines define *explicability* as one of the four key ethical values of AI systems, alongside *respect for human autonomy*, *prevention of harm*, and *fairness*, which are presented in the second level of Figure 4. Explicability is defined a bit broader than explainability, as it refers to the requirements for “*processes... to be transparent, the capabilities and purpose of AI systems openly communicated, and decisions – to the extent possible – explainable to those directly and indirectly affected*” [31]. This is essential for contestability and accountability. In contexts where full transparency is technically infeasible, varying levels of explainability may be applied.

The HLEG Guidelines operationalize general ethical principles by outlining seven key requirements for trustworthy AI, as depicted in the bottom layer of Figure 4. Transparency is the key requirement, most closely related to the principle of explicability and therefore the topic of this thesis. It encompasses an additional three points, not presented in Figure 4: explainability, traceability, and communication. *Explainability* is defined as the imperative to ensure make AI decisions understandable by humans, particularly when they have a significant impact on individuals. Explanations should be timely and tailored to the stakeholder's level of expertise (e.g., layperson, regulator, researcher).

The final policy document that is of key relevance to the genesis of the AI Act is the *2020 White Paper on Artificial Intelligence* [47]. With it, the Commission envisages the creation of two complementary ecosystems: **i) *ecosystem of excellence*** to foster innovation across the AI value

chain and create incentives for accelerated adoption; and **ii) *ecosystem of trust*** to ensure compliance with EU rules, including rules on fundamental and consumer rights, especially in high risks domains by considering the HLEG Ethics Guidelines. A key component for realizing this vision is the creation of a dedicated legal framework to enhance the EU's existing regulatory framework with specific rules for addressing AI challenges. One such explicitly listed challenge is the opacity of AI systems, which makes it difficult to verify how decisions are made and thus limits access to justice and contestability of decisions, contrary to the EU's core values. Still, the White Paper proposes that rules have sufficient flexibility to “*leave room to cater for further [AI] developments*” [47].

Based on these developments, in April 2021, the EU Commission published the first Proposal for the AI Act [48]. The proposal underwent substantial public consultation and numerous amendments [49]. Following the political agreement between the European Parliament and the Council in April 2021 [50], the AI Act [51] was adopted in the first half of 2024 and published in the Official Journal of the European Union on July 12, 2024. In line with the EU legislative procedure, the Act entered into force on August 1, 2024, that is, 20 days after its publication. However, its application will be phased in over several years. For this thesis, the most relevant dates are: **i)** August 2, 2026, when the AI Acts start applying for the high-risk systems listed in Annex III; and **ii)** August 2, 2027, when the AI Acts start applying for high-risk systems covered in Annex I. For more on Annex I and Annex III systems, view Section 2.1.3. From those dates, the core obligations for high-risk AI systems, including those related to transparency and explainability, become fully applicable to Annex III and Annex I systems, respectively.

As Figure 3 shows, the genesis of the AI Act did not stop with its enactment. Its practical meaning will continue to evolve through the implementation of guidelines, interpretative documents, the development of harmonized standards, and institutional and court practices. One such relevant development occurred with the publishing of the ***Guidelines on the definition of an artificial intelligence system established by AI Act*** (February 2025 Guidelines) [52]. They serve as an essential reference point for understanding the functional threshold that determines whether a system falls within the regulatory scope of the AI Act. Additionally, the evolution of the AI Act will be influenced by the *standards published by the European Standards Organizations* (ESOs). The Commission had tasked the ESOs with drafting standards to support conformity assessment of the AI Act [53], with an initial deadline of April 30, 2025. This deadline was previously postponed to the end of 2025 [54], but now there is

information indicating that the full spectrum of requested standards will not be delivered before early 2026 [53]. These delays have contributed to calls to postpone the implementation of the AI Act [54]. Finally, the evolution of the AI Act will be shaped in the years to come by the *practices adopted by courts and regulatory authorities*.

2.1.2 Scope of the AI Act

Before we go into the details of the obligations imposed by the AI Act, it is essential to clarify to which systems and actors the AI Act applies. Therefore, we cover the material, territorial, and personal scope of the AI Act.

2.1.2.1 Material scope: What is AI?

Although the AI Act is titled as a regulation on Artificial Intelligence, the concept of 'AI' itself lacks a universally accepted definition. That is why understanding the definition of AI systems is essential for establishing which types of systems fall within its scope. The primary definition is provided in Article 3, paragraph 1, and further elaborated upon in Recital 12 of the AI Act [51], with additional clarification offered in the February 2025 Guidelines [52].

Firstly, it is essential to distinguish between AI models and AI systems, as outlined in Recital 12. An AI model refers to the algorithmic or computational frameworks (e.g., neural networks or decision trees), and while essential, they are only one component of an AI system [55]. A complete system encompasses both software (e.g., user interfaces, APIs, monitoring tools) and hardware (e.g., storage, computing resources) necessary for deployment. This distinction is key because the AI Act regulates only AI System, not AI models. One exception is *general-purpose models* that are regulated, but these are not in the immediate interest of this thesis.

Nonetheless, determining if an AI System falls within the scope of the AI Act and what explainability obligations it entails, still to a large extent, depends on the nature of the underlying model. The initial proposal for the AI Act adopted a technique-based approach to defining AI by enumerating specific machine learning, logic, or statistical methods that constitute AI, while empowering the Commission to expand this list [48], [49]. This approach was heavily criticized as overly broad, failing to distinguish AI from traditional software, covering techniques that do not raise risks related to data, opacity, or safety, and misaligned with the OECD and HLEG definitions [2], [49]. This created the risk of regulatory overreach and inadvertently captured a vast range of conventional software [49].

In response, the technique-based approach was abandoned in favor of a function-based definition [49]. To fully grasp the content, one should refer to Article 3, paragraph 1 of the AI Act, its recitals, and the content of the February 2025 Guidelines. Based on that, for a system to be considered AI, it must exhibit seven key characteristics [51], [52]:

1. **Machine-based:** Means that the system is developed and runs on machines.
2. **Autonomy:** Functions with some independence from human control. Unlike traditional software, where rules are explicitly coded, AI systems derive rules during development and apply them at runtime based on data [56].
3. **Adaptiveness:** *May* evolve or self-improve through learning mechanisms without human input. The term “may” indicates that adaptiveness is typical but not required.
4. **Objectives:** Operates according to objectives, which are: explicit (directly encoded) or implicit (emerging from data or system behavior). Both can differ from the system’s intended purpose.
5. **Inference:** Generates output using techniques like machine learning, logic-based reasoning, or knowledge-based methods. This distinguishes AI from basic data processing.
6. **Outputs that influence physical or virtual environments,** which the February 2025 Guidelines clarify as four main types of outputs: **i)** predictions; **ii)** content; **iii)** recommendations; and **iv)** decisions.
7. **Interaction with the environment:** This means that the AI systems actively affect their surroundings, whether through tangible actions in the physical world or impacts within digital and software-based ecosystems.

This functional definition appears to be complicated and open to interpretation. So, the February 2025 Guidelines, in a way, revert to the initial approach and enumerate some machine learning and logic- or knowledge-based approaches that constitute AI. It also lists which systems are excluded from the definition: **i)** systems lacking meaningful inference, learning, or adaptiveness; **ii)** optimization tools (e.g., simulations, bandwidth allocation); **iii)** basic data processors (e.g., spreadsheets, filters); **iv)** rule-based heuristics (e.g., static chess engines); and **v)** simple predictors using trivial statistical rules (e.g., averages).

It should be noted that the AI Act excludes several categories of systems from its scope. These include AI systems used for military, defense, or national security purposes; open-source systems, unless they fall under prohibited, high-risk, or transparency obligations; systems used

by third countries or international organizations under law enforcement or judicial cooperation agreements, provided adequate safeguards are in place; and systems used solely for research, testing, or development, unless deployed in real-world conditions.

2.1.2.2 Territorial Scope and Personal Scope: Which are the key roles?

The AI Act adopts an expansive territorial scope to ensure prevention of regulatory circumvention and a “*level playing field and an effective protection of rights and freedoms*” [51]. The territorial scope is based on roles in the AI value chain, as defined in Article 3 and linked to Article 2.

The primary interest in this thesis is the role of *the provider*, as the obligations related to explainability are concentrated in this role. The reason for this lies in Article 14, paragraph 3 of the AI Act. According to it, oversight measures can be ensured by either (or both): **i)** the provider identifying and building the oversight measures; or **ii)** the provider identifying *and* the deployer implementing the measures. In any case, the role of the provider in choosing the appropriate tools is paramount and unavoidable. Also, providers bear the burden of making sure that a high-risk system is compliant with the AI Act before putting it on the market (Article 16).

The EU Act applies to providers regardless of place of establishment, as long as their AI system is *placed* on the EU market, *put into service* in the EU, or *has outputs* used in the EU. The AI Act purposefully avoids the term “developer,” focusing on the party responsible for the system, even if developed by others [56]. It applies to providers regardless of location if their AI System is used in the EU. There are two auxiliary roles of the provider. One is the importer, who is a person established or located in the EU that places on the market an AI system that bears the name of a third-country provider. Second, the distributor is a person other than the provider or the importer who makes an AI system available on the Union market. Besides the provider and its auxiliary roles, another important role is that of the deployer, who is a person using an AI system under their authority for non-personal, professional purposes.

It is important to note that, under Article 25, paragraph 1 of the AI Act, a distributor, importer, deployer or other third-party can “evolve” to become a provider if it: **i)** puts its name or trademark on a high-risk AI system; **ii)** substantially modifies a high-risk AI system so that it remains high-risk; or **iii)** modifies the intended purpose of a non-high-risk AI system in a way that it becomes a high-risk. In these cases, the initial provider ceases to play this role but still must cooperate with new providers by providing information and assistance.

2.1.3 High-risk AI Systems

The AI Act is built on a risk-based regulatory approach, which prescribes different obligations depending on the level of risk posed by AI systems. The EU has already used this regulatory approach in other areas such as banking and anti-money laundering. It reflects the principle of proportionality: regulatory requirements apply only to the extent necessary to mitigate identified risks [2].

The AI Act defines four levels of risk: *prohibited, high, limited, and minimal*. The analysis of this thesis focuses exclusively on high-risk systems, since transparency and, therefore, the explainability requirement only apply to them. At a general level, high-risk AI systems are those that are likely to cause “*significant harmful impact on the health, safety, and fundamental rights*” [51]. They fall into two main categories, as shown in Figure 5.

The first category includes products or safety components of products that meet two cumulative criteria: **i)** they fall under Union harmonization legislation listed in Annex I of the AI Act; and **ii)** they are subject to a third-party conformity assessment before being placed on the market or put into service. To clarify, *safety components* are those that perform a safety function or whose failure could endanger the health or safety of persons or property [51]. Under Annex 1, presented on the left side of Figure 5, products or safety components fall into two subcategories depending on the type of harmonization legislation to which they are subject:

- **Section A** lists harmonization laws under the New Legislative Framework. The AI Act applies directly to systems covered by that legislation.
- **Section B** lists several sector-specific harmonization regulations that will be amended by Articles 102 to 109 of the AI Act to integrate the AI Act’s requirements of high-risk systems into them. To these systems, the AI Act applies indirectly via the amendments.

The second category of high-risk systems, shown on the right side of Figure 5, is a stand-alone AI system that “*in light of their intended purpose... pose a high risk of harm to the health and safety or the fundamental rights of persons*” [51]. This category covers eight sensitive areas: biometrics, education, critical infrastructure, labor issues, essential public services, law enforcement, administration of justice, migration, and democratic process. These sensitive areas are listed in Annex III, where, under each area, covered use cases are listed. Exceptions to this category may apply in cases where the AI system is designed to carry out a narrowly

defined procedural function, enhance the outcome of an already completed human task, identify patterns or anomalies in decision-making without substituting human judgment, or support a preparatory activity.

Figure 5. Overview of high-risk AI systems under the EU AI Act.

The AI Act defines high-risk AI systems as either (i) safety components of products covered by EU harmonization laws (Annex I), or (ii) stand-alone systems used in sensitive areas like biometrics, education, and law enforcement (Annex III). Systems in Annex I are subject to direct or indirect regulation, while Annex III systems must meet criteria related to potential harm, with some exemptions under Article 6(3).

Reproduced from: Voigt and Hullén, The EU AI Act: Answers to Frequently Asked Questions [42].

2.1.4 Requirements of high-risk systems: Is there an explainability obligation?

Articles 8 to 15 of the AI Act establish the core requirements for high-risk AI systems, aimed at mitigating risks, ensuring a high level of trustworthiness, and protecting fundamental rights and public safety [51]. The provisions are rooted in HLEG's Ethics Guidelines and should therefore be interpreted through the lens of these ethical principles [42]. Seven key requirements of the AI Act must be applied to all high-risk AI Systems. For this thesis, the most relevant provisions are those related to transparency and the provision of information to deployers (Article 13) and human oversight (Article 14), as the explainability obligations are derived from them. Due consideration should also be given to clauses on the risk management system (Article 9), as the requirements cannot be met without directly assessing the impact or lack of explainability. Similarly, at least some deliberation is needed regarding explainability and technical documentation (Article 11). This thesis will omit reviewing the relationship between explainability and the other three requirements: data and data governance (Article 10), record-keeping (Article 12), and accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity (Article 15). In these three requirements, explainability is not of direct importance, though, based on the discussion in Subchapter 1.3, it can be argued that it still has at least some indirect importance.

The most relevant provision for this thesis is Article 13, which establishes the criterion of transparency for high-risk AI Systems. Article 13, paragraph 1 mandates that high-risk AI systems be developed in a way “*to ensure that their operation is sufficiently transparent to enable deployers to interpret a system's output and use it appropriately*” [51]. In addition, the system must include instructions for use that, among other things, cover: **i)** human oversight measures as referred to in Article 14, including “*technical measures put in place to facilitate the interpretation of the outputs*” [51]; and **ii)** the system's capabilities and limitations.

The obligations are further crystallized by Article 14, paragraph 1 of the AI Act, which necessitates that high-risk systems are “*designed and developed [with] ... appropriate human-machine interface tools, that can be effectively overseen by natural persons...*” [51]. Article 14, paragraph 3 acknowledges that oversight methods must be proportionate to the system's risks, level of autonomy, and context of deployment. As the following subchapter will demonstrate, this context-dependent proportionality is reflected in most current standards

related to AI. Subject to proportionality, according to Article 14, paragraph 4, oversight tools need to enable:

- i) monitoring a system for anomalies, dysfunctions, and unexpected performance (subparagraph a);
- ii) remain aware of tendencies to over-rely on an AI system's output, i.e., automation bias (subparagraph b);
- iii) correctly interpret outputs, especially by considering interpretation tools (subparagraph c);
- iv) decide to override or disregard the output of a system (subparagraph d).

This formulation of Articles 13 and 14 has spurred an ongoing debate. Some authors like Panigutti et al. [57], argue that explainability is not mandatory because it has not been explicitly mentioned in the text, and that transparency should be achieved by providing relevant documentation and information to the user, rather than the use of specific XAI tools. Others, G. Pavlidis, take the position that explainability is a fundamental principle of the AI Act, even though exact standards are still not determined or tested in practice [2].

The position of this thesis is that, having in mind the emphasis on explainability in the genesis of the AI Act and the positions of most standard-setting organizations, this clause can only be interpreted as mandating the inclusion of interfaces that provide explanations of the output, which, in cases of using black box models, requires resorting to XAI. The assertion that transparency requirements can be met solely through documentation is unacceptable because it is based on an interpretation of Article 13 while overlooking the requirements of Article 14. But even if only Article 13 is read in a void, to be able to document “*interpretation tools*” (Article 13 paragraph 3 subparagraph b) and “*features that facilitate explanations*,” these tools and features must exist in the first place. In addition, it is challenging to envision how a human can effectively manage a system if the human-machine interface tools fail to display the system's actions. Finally, it seems impossible to present the “*capabilities and limitations*” of black box systems without using XAI.

While of secondary importance to this thesis, Articles 9 and 11 still warrant mention. A risk management system (Article 9) cannot be considered complete without addressing the risks that stem from the opacity or misinterpretation of AI outputs. Similarly, the purpose of the technical documentation requirement (Article 11) is to demonstrate compliance with the AI Act, and according to Annex IV, this documentation must include an “*assessment of the human*

oversight measures ... including an assessment of the technical measures needed to facilitate the interpretation of the outputs” [51].

2.1.5 Oversight: How will compliance be checked?

Whether the system complies with the transparency and oversight requirements listed in the previous subchapter will be established by a combination of *ex ante conformity assessments* with *ex post enforcement* to ensure that high-risk AI systems meet regulatory requirements before market entry, in the spirit of the New Legislative Framework that the AI Adopts [2].

Ex ante conformity assessment might involve self-assessment or control by a third party. In both cases, if harmonized standards referenced in the Official Journal of the European Union or common specifications developed by the Commission are fully applied, a presumption of conformity is granted to a system. Internal checks performed in accordance with Annex VI are sufficient for systems covered by points 2 to 8 of Annex III. More sensitive systems require external conformity assessment procedures conducted by *notified bodies*, which are independent entities accredited to perform conformity assessments of high-risk systems by *notifying authorities*, which are institutions designated by Member States. To finalize the *ex-ante* conformity process, providers must draft and sign an EU Declaration of Conformity, which states that their AI system complies with all applicable provisions. After completing all the necessary steps, the system can bear the CE marking, signifying conformity with EU requirements and enabling its free circulation within the single market.

After placing the system on the market, under Article 72 of the AI Act, providers will have to plan and execute post-market monitoring that will be used to “*collect, document and analyze relevant data*” [51]. Though there are no particular sources to cite, it logically follows that the technical measures used to facilitate interpretation under Article 14 should be part of the post-market monitoring.

Ex post enforcement will be carried out by national Market Surveillance Authorities (MSAs) designated by each EU Member State. Under Article 70, paragraph 1 of the AI Act, each member state is required to have at least one MSA. In addition, Article 74, paragraph 3 of the AI Act gives a default rule, where for systems covered in Annex I, the authority responsible for the listed harmonization laws will be an MSA for that particular system. Therefore, it is conceivable that a member state may have multiple MSAs, which can result in a fragmented

surveillance landscape [58]. Voigt and Hullén [42] explain that MSAs may intervene without prior suspicion or in response to specific complaints, whereby they will have broad investigation authorizations that include simple activities, such as access to technical documentation, event logs, and source code, as well as more complex investigation powers, including reverse engineering.

For infringement of obligations related to high-risk systems, including the articles discussed in the previous subsection, the MSAs can impose a sanction of up to 3% of the annual turnover or up to €15 million, whichever is higher. When deciding on the size of the sanction, the MSA will consider the mitigating and aggravating circumstances as outlined in Article 99, paragraph of the AI Act. Among these are the: **i)** nature, gravity, and duration of the infringement and its consequences; **ii)** previous fines and conduct; **iii)** size, annual turnover, and market share of the operator; **iv)** financial benefits gained or losses avoided from the infringement; **v)** degree of cooperation to remedy the infringement and mitigate adverse effects; **vi)** degree of responsibility, considering the technical and organizational measures implemented; **vii)** manner in which the infringement became known; **viii)** intentional or negligent nature of the infringement; and **xi)** actions taken by the operator to mitigate harm to affected persons.

2.2 The global normative context

To fully understand the AI Act and any adverse effects on competitiveness derived from regulatory divergence between the EU and other jurisdictions, it is essential to consider the global context. That is why this subchapter examines how explainability is addressed internationally through policy frameworks, national legislation, and standards bodies.

2.2.1 International level approaches

On the international level, numerous efforts have been made to define what responsible AI entails. Almost invariably, such definitions contain the requirements of transparency, interpretability, and explainability. Here we list the three primary international documents that deal with responsible AI and their relevance to the subject matter of this thesis:

- **The OECD AI Principles (2019)** [59] that is endorsed by over 40 countries, affirm the importance of transparency and accountability. Principle 7 specifically addresses the issue of explainability, stating that those affected by AI systems should have access to meaningful information in order for decisions to be understood and challenged.

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- **The UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence (2021)** [60] lists explainability as a fundamental pillar for ensuring respect of human rights and fundamental freedoms. It acknowledges that context matters and that irreversible or impactful decisions merit higher standards.
 - **The G20 AI Principles (2019)** [61] stress the importance of traceability and explainability in AI systems. Principle 1.3 requires AI actors to provide meaningful, understandable information with the goals of fostering understanding of AI and allowing decisions to be challenged.

2.2.2 National level approaches

While many jurisdictions have issued state-backed ethical principles, guidelines, or codes of conduct, only a few have enacted substantive laws to date [36]. Nonetheless, across nearly all ethical, technical, and many legal frameworks, explainability is consistently recognized as a key principle for ensuring transparency, trust, and accountability in AI systems.

In the **United States** (US), attempts to regulate AI at the federal level have so far been unsuccessful. Early bills like the *Algorithmic Accountability Act* of 2019 [62] and the *Algorithmic Fairness Act of 2020* [63] did not become law, though they contained clauses on transparency and the right to review and contest algorithmic decisions. The most comprehensive federal proposal to date, the *Algorithmic Accountability Act of 2023* [64] proposes requirements similar to those in the AI Act, but lists explainability explicitly as a requirement. The only enacted federal legislation is the *National Artificial Intelligence Initiative Act of 2020* [65]. It focuses solely on research and development but supports explainability by funding projects aimed at developing trustworthy AI, including XAI.

Despite attempts at regulation, it is unlikely that any regulation will be implemented in the foreseeable future. The US regulatory ideology is based on a techno-libertarian ethos and the belief that its technological leadership is grounded in the unregulated marketplace [66]. This ideology is exemplified by the fact that *President Biden's Executive Order on Safe, Secure, and Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence of 2023* [67] was swiftly rescinded by President Trump upon assuming office as being a part of many „unpopular, inflationary, illegal, and radical practices” [68]. As a result, not only does the US lack federal AI regulations, but it also lacks comparable regulations to the EU’s data protection and content regulation, and is much milder in its approach to competition regulation [66].

In the US, regulatory initiatives have been more successful on a **state level**, reflecting two distinct approaches. *Colorado's Artificial Intelligence Act* [69] mirrors to a degree the EU's horizontal and risk-based approach. It touches on the point of explainability when it mandates disclosing the manner and degree in which an AI system contributed to making a *consequential decision*. In contrast, California's legislative efforts, including the unsuccessful Frontier Artificial Intelligence Models Act (SB 1047) [70] have pivoted toward a fragmented, sector-specific regulatory framework, reflecting an *ad hoc*, vertical approach [71]. As a result, examining the multiple acts for explainability relevant clauses is beyond the scope of this work.

Similarly to California, **China** has adopted a vertical and iterative regulatory model regarding AI, focusing on specific use cases, while allowing regulators to update rules in response to technological change [72]. Its regulatory goals are aligning AI with the Communist Party of China's agenda and control, managing algorithmic influence on online content, and promoting China as a global leader in AI [72], [73]. The most notable AI-related regulations are the *Interim Measures for the Management of Generative Artificial Intelligence Services* [74] and the *Deep Synthesis Technology Regulations* [75] however, they do not address explainability. Similar to the EU, the *Personal Information Protection Law* [76], often compared to the GDPR [77] provides individuals with the right to an explanation when subjected to automated decision-making (Article 24, paragraph 3). Likewise, the *Internet Information Service Algorithmic Recommendation Management Provisions* [78] obliges service providers to “*give an explanation and bear related liability*” [78] when algorithmic recommendations significantly affect users' rights and interests. By contrast, China's ethical frameworks take a more explicit stance on explainability. The *Governance Principles for a New Generation of Artificial Intelligence: Develop Responsible Artificial Intelligence* (2019) [79], in one of its eight principles, lists the requirement that AI systems be “*safe and controllable*” [79] emphasizing continuous improvement of explainability. Similarly, *Ethical Norms for New Generation Artificial Intelligence* [80] calls for improving explainability at every stage of algorithm design and implementation.

Brazil is likely to follow the EU's lead in AI regulation, mirroring its previous alignment with the GDPR through the enactment of the *Lei Geral de Proteção de Dados* in 2020 [81]. Although a detailed analysis of Brazil's proposed AI Regulation was limited due to linguistic barriers, multiple sources indicate significant parallels to the AI Act [82]. Obligations reportedly include

the requirements for AI systems to be both explainable and auditable, as well as granting individuals the explicit right to obtain explanations regarding AI-driven decisions [83].

Most other countries have neither enacted nor proposed legislation to regulate AI systems. Instead, they approach AI regulation with voluntary guidelines and ethical codes. In this direction, **Australia** has adopted its *AI Ethics Principles (2019)* [84] that identifies eight essential ethical principles and has complemented this with a practical guide on implementing the principles, the *Voluntary AI Safety Standard* [85], which recommends opting for more interpretable and explainable AI.

Saudi Arabia and the **United Arab Emirates (UAE)**, two countries with significant AI ambitions, have established impressive ethical codes. Principle 5 of Saudi Arabia's AI Ethical Principles of September 2023 [86] states that "*AI systems must be built with a high level of... explainability... particularly those that may lead to detrimental effects on data subjects...*" Furthermore, the ethical code is supplemented by two guidelines for government entities [87] and private entities [88], both of which list explainability as a fundamental principle. Likewise, UAE's AI Ethics: Principles & Guidelines [89] features Principle 4, which commits to making AI systems "*as explainable as technically possible.*"

India, like other countries with AI ambitions, has developed one of the most comprehensive ethical frameworks globally. Its *Responsible AI #AIForAll* initiative is published in two parts: *Part 1 – Principles for Responsible AI* [32] and *Part 2 – Operationalizing Principles for Responsible AI* [90]. Part 1 states that "*in cases where the law requires an explanation of individual decisions, it becomes prohibitive to use [such models], even if the models are highly accurate*" [32]. Finally, **Africa**, the continent poised to become the world's most populous socio-economic region, has accepted explainability as a foundational element of trustworthy and inclusive AI governance, in the *African Union's Continental AI Strategy* [91].

2.2.3 Approaches of standard-setting organizations

The **ISO/IEC 42001: Information technology – Artificial Intelligence – Management system** (ISO/IEC 42001) [92] highlights the non-transparent and non-explainable nature of automated decision-making as a central concern when implementing an AI management system. Accordingly, it identifies explainability as a key objective in the development of responsible AI systems, alongside other objectives such as fairness, accountability, safety,

reliability, and accessibility. Crucially, the standard suggests that the specific form of explainability should be context-dependent, shaped by factors such as applicable legal requirements, the intended purpose of the AI system, as well as prevailing cultural, societal, and ethical norms.

Other standards within the ISO/IEC framework also emphasize explainability as a key characteristic of AI systems. **The ISO/IEC 23053:2022: Framework for Artificial Intelligence (AI) Systems Using Machine Learning** [93] highlights that explainability is critical throughout the entire AI system lifecycle, from inception and design through development, verification, validation, deployment, operation, monitoring, and re-evaluation. Furthermore, **ISO/IEC 42005: Information technology — Artificial intelligence (AI) — AI system impact assessment** [94] advises that when making impact assessments, organizations should assess the reasonably foreseeable benefits and harms of explainability for each identified relevant stakeholder. In particular, it warns of risks such as: **i)** misinterpretation or misunderstanding of system outputs by stakeholders; **ii)** the inability of stakeholders to rely on the system for informed decision-making; and **iii)** the risk of overreliance and automation bias. At the same time, the standard notes potential benefits of explainability, including enhanced trust and improved error traceability.

The **National Institute of Standards and Technology** has developed two key documents that highlight explainability as a foundational principle of ethical AI. According to the *AI Risk Management Framework* (RMF) [34], accountability requires transparency, and transparency requires explicability. The RMF recognizes that explainability may conflict with other characteristics of trustworthy AI, such as being valid and reliable, safe, secure, and resilient, accountable and transparent, privacy-enhanced, and fair with harmful bias managed. For instance, increasing explainability may reduce privacy or predictive performance. The RMF emphasizes that deciding on trade-offs depends on “*values at play in the relevant context*” [34]. The *NISTIR 8312: Four Principles of Explainable AI* [95] defines what makes an AI system explainable, a topic we will revisit when discussing the challenges organizations face in determining what constitutes a good explanation.

Finally, the **IEEE Standard for Transparency of Autonomous Systems (IEEE Std 7001-2021)** [35] provides a framework for setting out clearly defined, testable levels of transparency. It mandates explainability as part of higher transparency levels for many stakeholders and

provides human-understandable reasons behind decisions, tailored to the comprehension levels of the stakeholder groups. We will return to it when discussing the quality of explanations.

2.3 Closing the chapter on legal aspects of explainability

Two trends are reflected in both the AI Act and the discussed global and national ethical codes, standards, laws, and bills. First, there is a shared expectation that AI decisions, particularly those with high impact, must be understandable to affected individuals, and when using black box models this necessitates the use of XAI. Second, there is widespread recognition that trade-offs are inevitable between achieving explainability on the one hand and preserving accuracy, privacy, and proprietary interests on the other. Based on this, it follows that explainability should be calibrated to the context. What is notable is that some frameworks go so far as to say that there are use cases where a complete, *reliable explanation becomes a condition sine non*. This position can easily be fit into the AI Act, especially when viewed from the lens of the HLEG Guidelines' principle of lawful AI. Namely, there are existing rules under which a full explanation supported by facts is a fundamental element.

“Explainability and interpretability techniques are not alternative choices for many real problems...[as] XAI can be dangerous for high-stakes decisions to a degree that the other is not.” [12] – Cynthia Rudin

For this thesis, it is clear that the AI Act requires explainability for high-risk AI systems, primarily to enable meaningful human oversight, but also to understand the capabilities and limitations of AI Systems and allow individuals to understand and challenge decisions. In addition, this thesis proposes that, *de facto*, the AI Act's high-risk tier covered in 2.1.3 may be further split into three unwritten sub-groups based on the explainability or interpretability approach that needs to be taken:

1. **Mandatory interpretability use cases**, where the provided explanation is fully theoretically sound to the extent that there can be no reasonable doubt that the explanation is valid. The use cases in this category are *very narrow and pertain to procedural justice or cases where other fundamental rights are directly at issue*. Some typical examples include AI-assisted judicial decision-making, a bail recommendations system, asylum determinations, or administrative procedures that involve crucial rights

of a subject. As Chapter 3 will show, currently, almost exclusively interpretable systems satisfy this criterion.

2. **Strict explainability use cases**, where only the soundest explanation techniques can be used, cover situations in which using a *black box is unavoidable for ensuring broader coverage of essential services or saving lives*. One example would be an AI system used for allocating public subsidies, such as energy or housing support. The use of a black box would be justified by the significant efficiency gains and the ability to resolve individual requests quickly. However, strong explainability must still be ensured to provide individuals with clear and comprehensible explanations, particularly when a benefit is denied, to safeguard their right to contest the decision. Another type of use case involves situations where *a black box offers a significant accuracy advantage over human judgment*. A typical example is an AI system used in radiology for early cancer detection, where the system may significantly outperform doctors. Yet, its output must still be explained in a way that is understandable to both clinicians and patients.
3. **Balanced explainability use cases** where a lighter or *more pragmatic level of explainability can be accepted in exchange for competing societal or economic benefits*. In these cases, performance, scalability, or economic viability may justify the use of looser explainability standards, provided that careful risk management is employed. One example is an AI system for predictive maintenance of critical infrastructure, where significant economic gains can be achieved, but the risks of weak explanations are minimal. Another example is the preventive flagging of individuals for medical check-ups based on the scanning of electronic health records (EHRs). While such flagging does not represent a diagnosis, false positives may still subject individuals to unnecessary testing or stress. Nonetheless, the societal benefits of large-scale coverage may outweigh the risks posed by insufficient explanations.

3 Explainability in the technological context

There are two widely recognized approaches for solving the opaqueness of models [6], [11], [21]. Applied on the level of AI Systems, this means that opacity can be avoided by:

- i. **Interpretability** - basing AI Systems on intrinsically interpretable models or putting it in another way: avoiding opaque models. Interpretability is a *passive property*, as

it inherently exists in interpretable models and for that reason has even been called *in-model interpretability* [17] or *ex ante interpretability* [7]; or

- ii. ***Explainability*** - including tools in the AI System that are based on techniques that help understand the opaque models. These techniques are called *post hoc* because they are applied after the model has been trained and are decoupled from the underlying model [11]. This makes explainability an *active property* because it does not exist in the model and needs to be established with subsequent techniques [17].

Based on the above-cited realization, this chapter examines the technical foundations and practical implementation of the two primary paths toward achieving compliance under the AI Act: utilizing inherently interpretable models or applying post-hoc explainability techniques to black-box models. Subchapter 3.1 begins by examining various aspects of inherently interpretable models, including the key characteristics that influence interpretability, the trade-offs between white-box and black-box models, and the potential downsides of relying on interpretable models. The subchapter concludes with an analysis of four key types of interpretable models, incorporating scholarly opinions, experimental findings, and visual presentation of explanation artifacts. Next, Subchapter 3.2 focuses on post-hoc explainability techniques (XAI), beginning with a discussion of their core weaknesses, common classification frameworks, and relevant evaluation benchmarks. The subchapter then proceeds with a detailed review of widely used model-agnostic methods, covering both global and local methods in two separate sections. The initial purpose was also to cover a couple of model-specific approaches in a separate section, but due to time constraints, this idea was abandoned.

3.1 Basing AI Systems on intrinsically interpretable models

Though explainability is of key interest in this thesis, the main goal is to explore *how explainability fits into a strategy for compliance with the AI Act*. One viable compliance strategy is to avoid the need for achieving explainability by relying on inherently interpretable models. To paraphrase one author, using interpretable models is the best “explainability” technique, as they allow perfect representation of the model [16]. Furthermore, as discussed in the previous chapter, in certain use cases, explainability techniques may be insufficient to comply with legal or ethical standards, and interpretable models are the only viable option.

Basing AI Systems on white-box models offers several advantages, particularly in the context of compliance. They provide a certainty that the relationships between the inputs and outputs

are clear [7]. In addition, explanations of white box models are faithful to what the model accurately computes [10]; unlike explainability, which yields unstable and uncertain results. As a result, white box models have been favored in high-stakes AI systems [96].

White box models are typically created by imposing restrictions on the choice of models to the class of intrinsically interpretable models [6], [96]. However, white boxes can become too difficult to interpret, especially if they contain multiple parameters, non-linear relations, or unintuitive features. Lipton [97] has called interpretability a myth, as interpretability ceases to exist if more than a handful of parameters or weights are introduced. This has been referred to as the transparency paradox, where an abundance of available information makes it difficult to extract the relevant information [17]. So it follows that models are interpretable only when they have “*human-reasonable sizes*” [9]. Authors have examined the threshold that separates a comprehensible model from an incomprehensible one. Molnar, for example, has said that “*any feature space with more than 3 dimensions is simply inconceivable for humans*” [6].

That is why other restrictions are also applied that make the model understandable to humans, such as monotonicity [10], [14], [11], structural constraints [14], [10],[98] additivity [14], [10], physical constraints that come from domain knowledge [14], [10], [11], sparsity [10], [11], decomposability [97], [99], [9], causality [11], and other constraints.

3.1.1 Assessing interpretability

It is essential to note that even models built with the same underlying algorithm can exhibit varying **levels of interpretability**. Just think about a linear model with eight parameters and one with 150 parameters. Authors such as Lipton [97], Molnar [6], Sudjianto and Zhang [100], Guidotti et al. [9], and Belle and Papantonis [99] have proposed various parameters for assessing the interpretability of models. Collectively, they highlight concepts such as:

Simulatability - the extent to which a model can be understood by a human in its entirety at once. It is measured by the ability of a human to take the input data along with the model’s parameters and, within a reasonable time, manually compute the prediction step by step.

Decomposability - the degree to which each component of the model (inputs, parameters, and calculations) can be intuitively understood and interpreted individually. This allows a model to be broken down into interpretable parts that contribute to the final prediction and is relevant for local or modular interpretability.

Algorithmic transparency - the ability to understand the procedure for generating outputs.

Additivity - the characteristic of a model where the overall output is a sum of the individual effects of each feature. This structure supports interpretability by making the influence of each feature explicit and separable.

Sparsity - the degree to which a model relies on a small subset of features for making predictions. Sparse models are easier to interpret because they focus attention on the most relevant information.

Linearity - the property where changes in input lead to proportional, predictable changes in output. Linear relationships are inherently easier for humans to grasp and verify.

Smoothness - the extent to which small changes in input lead to small, continuous changes in output. Smooth models avoid abrupt shifts, making them more intuitive and user-friendly.

Monotonicity - the quality of a model to preserve a consistent directional relationship between inputs and outputs. For example, if an increase in income should always result in an increase in credit score, a monotonic model will reflect that expectation, thereby enhancing trust and alignment with domain knowledge.

Visualizability - the ability to represent a model or its components in visual formats such as charts or graphs. Visualization aids understanding, explanation, and error detection.

Interaction - the capacity of a model to incorporate or reveal interactions between features, either inherently or through feature engineering. Understanding how features interact enhances the explanatory depth of the model.

Building inherently interpretable models goes beyond *selecting a particular model architecture to also using features (inputs) that make sense to humans*. According to Sudjianto and Zhang [100], this involves several key aspects:

- **Using features that have real-world meaning**, so that users can relate the input directly to something they understand in practice.
- **Ensuring that features follow expected behavior**, such as increasing income leading to a higher credit score, known as *monotonicity*, based on expert knowledge.

- **Relying on features that are likely to have a cause-and-effect relationship** with the outcome, rather than just correlations; these are called *causal features*.
- **Designing features in a way that keeps them simple**, for example by using methods that keep only the most essential parts (this is called *sparse projection*) to make the model cleaner and easier to interpret.

3.1.2 The accuracy-interpretability trade-off debate

There is a widely held belief that using interpretable models entails sacrificing accuracy or that accuracy and interpretability are inversely related, as explained by Kerrigan [13]. According to this view, complex models, such as neural networks, offer higher predictive accuracy by capturing intricate patterns and processing large and diverse datasets. In contrast, simpler models like linear regression provide transparent decision-making but may fail to capture complex, non-linear relationships and diverse types of data. Figure 6 illustrates the interpretability–complexity continuum, where simpler models are more interpretable, while more complex models offer reduced transparency in exchange for improved predictive performance.

Figure 6. The interpretability–complexity continuum of common machine learning models. As model complexity increases - from linear and logistic regression to deep neural networks - interpretability tends to decrease. Simpler models like linear regression offer high transparency, while more complex models such as random forests and deep neural networks require post-hoc explanation methods. *Reproduced from Hsieh et al., A Comprehensive Guide to Explainable AI: From Classical Models to LLMs, 2024 [101]*

However, some authors have questioned the interpretability-accuracy axiom [10], [14], [96]. For example, Rudin [10] claims that this trade-off is a myth for many real-world problems. She argues that when dealing with meaningful features, there is no significant difference between complex classifiers, such as neural networks, and simpler classifiers, like logistic regression. Additionally, she criticizes the practice of making comparisons using static datasets. In reality, the process of building an interpretable model is iterative, and the data are refined after

interpreting the results. According to her, this iterative process can even reverse the accuracy/interpretability trade-off.

The belief in interpretability-accuracy trade-off has contributed to an explosion of XAI techniques, while interpretable models are not even considered as a possible solution [10], [102]. This is problematic because some use cases require high levels of certainty in explanations, and, as will be shown in the Section 3.2.1, XAI methods are often unreliable and sometimes even misleading [10].

3.1.3 Other potential downsides of interpretable models

Developers face unique technical challenges when creating inherently interpretable models [103]. Rudin [10] notes that the main one is solving optimization problems that may be computationally demanding. She also notes that building interpretable models relies heavily on dealing with data issues, which can slow down deployment. Furthermore, she claims that interpretability depends on applying specific constraints that require domain understanding to define, and that interpretable models prevent companies from protecting their intellectual property and trade secrets, as anyone could understand and replicate their models. Finally, an additional weakness is that there is a very limited number of machine learning models considered white box [30].

3.1.4 Overview of main white box models

This section provides an overview of the most widely used white-box models, which have inherent interpretability. It examines how regression models, decision trees, rule-based systems, and interpretable neural networks can support AI Systems to fully avoid the need to implement XAI techniques and thus achieve compliance with the AI Act.

3.1.4.1 Regression Models

Linear regression is one of the most interpretable types of models [99]. The key reasons are that [6], [99]: **i)** relations between the features and target are linear, therefore intuitively understandable by humans; **ii)** there are reliable metrics for interpreting the model even for people with basic mathematics skills; **iii)** they have been used for decades by various experts, so there is collective experience with linear models. In addition, despite their simplicity, linear models are a powerful tool that offers interpretability and, therefore, are a go-to choice in high-

impact sectors such as finance and healthcare [101], . In the group of regression models, we list linear regression, logistic regression, and extensions of traditional regression models.

Let's start with interpreting **linear and logistic regression**, as presented by Molnar [6]. In linear models, each feature weight represents its direct contribution to the prediction. For a numerical feature, “*increasing the numerical feature by one unit changes the estimated outcome by its weight*” [6]. A binary feature changes the prediction when switching from the reference category (0) to the other category (1), thereby “*chang[ing] the estimated outcome by the feature's weight*” [6]. Interpreting categorical features with multiple categories is the same as interpreting binary features because, via “one-hot-encoding,” each categorical feature is turned into multiple rows of binary features. There are also great visualization techniques for interpreting linear regression models, such as: **i)** weight plots that display weights allotted by the model; **ii)** effect plots that show the contribution of a combination of weight and feature, thus displaying the range of combined contribution. When it comes to classification tasks, **logistic regression** is used to predict values that represent probabilities. To achieve this, the linear output is passed through the logistic function, which transforms the result into a probability. Due to this transformation, when interpreting the model, it is essential to keep in mind “*that weights do not influence the probability linearly any longer*” [6].

🔍 Top Features (by absolute weight):

	Feature	Coefficient
24	Fluoroscopy: 0 Vessels	1.408001
7	Chest Pain: Typical Angina	-1.141996
23	Thalassemia: Reversible Defect	1.029392
26	Fluoroscopy: 2 Vessels	-0.866285
10	Chest Pain: Asymptomatic	0.784774
6	Sex: Male	-0.715288
19	ST Slope: Flat	-0.629718
22	Thalassemia: Fixed Defect	0.592385
20	ST Slope: Downsloping	0.577307
5	Sex: Female	0.572847

Figure 7. Top Features Table by absolute weight for a global interpretation of a logistic regression model.

The table displays the most influential predictors, ranked by the absolute value. Positive coefficients (e.g., "Fluoroscopy: 0 Vessels") indicate an increase in the log-odds of heart disease, while negative coefficients (e.g., "Chest Pain: Typical Angina") suggest the opposite effect.

The use of logistic regression to interpret models and their predictions is best illustrated with a simple model example from the experiment conducted for this thesis. After training a regression model on the UCI Heart Disease dataset, we can get a Top Features Table. It shows how the global importance of features can be analyzed in logistic regression, as shown in Figure 7.

$$\frac{\text{odds}_{x_j+k}}{\text{odds}_{x_j}} = \exp(k \cdot \beta_j)$$

Figure 8. Formula for interpreting logistic regression coefficients in terms of odds ratios.

Let's say we want to understand how experiencing *asymptomatic chest pain* affects the likelihood of heart disease. The logistic regression model assigns a coefficient of 0.785 to this binary feature, as shown in Figure 7. This means that having asymptomatic chest pain increases the log-odds of heart disease by 0.785. To get a more intuitive number, we can convert the log-odds into an odds ratio using the formula listed in Figure 8, where x_j is the value of the predictor variable, k is the number of units by which x_j increases, and β_j is the logistic regression coefficient for that predictor. If we apply the formula on the particular variable, we compute $\exp(1 \cdot 0,785) = \exp(0,785) \approx 2.193$. This tells us that, all else being equal, a patient with asymptomatic chest pain has odds of heart disease that are approximately 119% higher than those without it.

Figure 9. Plots for local interpretation of a decision made by a logistic regression model.

Local interpretation of instance #0 offers two perspectives:
Log-odds contributions (left) and percentage change in odds (right).

We can also easily produce local explanation artefacts for logistic regression. The visualization in Figure 9 shows how instance number 0 was locally interpreted during the experiment. This interpretation is perfectly stable and computed fast. However, the plot also *illustrates the limitations of interpretability*. While the plots highlight the most influential features, interpreting the magnitude of log-odds contributions or even percentage shifts in odds is not intuitive. The notion of log-odds lacks real-world anchoring, while even a 100% increase in odds may not correspond to a meaningful change in predicted probability. This limits the practical usability of the insights, despite the model's transparency and consistency.

Basic regression models have four major weaknesses [6], [101]. One limitation is that linear models assume a linear relationship between the features and the target variable, which is rarely true in real-world circumstances. The other is that multicollinearity distorts the estimation of coefficients, which is also very applicable in reality. Third, they presuppose a normal distribution of variables. Finally, logistic regression is only suitable for binary classifications.

To improve these weaknesses, multiple extensions of the traditional regression models have been introduced [6]. In this thesis, we will cover one such extension: **the Generalized Additive Models (GAMs)**. They were invented in the 1980s to extend linear models to capture non-linear relationships, such as U-shaped or threshold effects, while maintaining the additive structure of classical linear models, i.e., their interpretability [96], [101]. As the formula in Figure 10 shows – where β_0 is the intercept and each $f_i(x_i)$ represents a smooth, possibly non-linear function of the individual feature x_i – the model maintains an additive structure by modeling features with a smooth nonlinear function [6]. This structure offers both decomposability and additivity, and makes it possible to visualize and model the magnitude and direction of the influence using shape functions, making the model transparent and verifiable by a human [96], [14]. It should be noted that GAMs are more accurately described as a family of models rather than a single model type. One powerful example is **GA²M**, which extends GAMs by incorporating pairwise feature interactions. Marcinkevičs and Vogt demonstrate that GA²M “perform on par with uninterpretable techniques in tabular datasets” [14].

$$f(\mathbf{X}) = \beta_0 + f_1(X_1) + f_2(X_2) + \dots + f_k(X_k)$$

Figure 10. Generalized Additive Model (GAM) structure

3.1.4.2 Decision Trees

Decision trees are another white-box approach that yields inherently interpretable models, as they contain a set of conditions arranged in a hierarchical manner [99] and represented in a flowchart-like structure [101]. If the tree is sufficiently short, it can even be memorized by a human, which makes them a *par excellence* simulatable models [99]. Even if the tree is long and not simulatable, then it is still decomposable. Therefore, trees are often used in cases when understanding the model is essential [99], [101].

Global feature importance in decision trees measures how much each feature contributes to the overall predictive performance by evaluating how often and how effectively it is used to split the data [6]. The raw importance of a feature is calculated by summing the impurity reductions (e.g., using Gini impurity or mean squared error) at all the nodes where that feature is used to split. In simple terms, every time the tree splits on a feature, we record how much that split reduces impurity, and then we sum up these reductions across the entire tree. To make these values comparable across features, we normalize them: each feature's total importance is divided by the sum of importances for all features. This provides a percentage that represents the portion of the tree's total impurity reduction attributable to a given feature. These normalized percentages can then be used to rank the features, providing a global interpretation of how influential each feature is in the model's decision-making process.

Figure 11 shows a global feature importance plot for a decision tree model trained on the UCI Heart Disease dataset. The plot provides a clear and intuitive representation of the importance of each feature in predicting the outcome. One obvious limitation is that *the plot does not indicate the direction of feature contributions*. Thus, it is clear which features are more important, but it is not possible to determine whether a feature has a positive or negative impact.

Figure 11. Global feature importance plot for a decision tree model.

The bar chart shows the relative contribution of each feature to the model's predictions, with "Chest Pain: Typical Angina" being the most influential. While helpful in identifying key variables, this plot does not convey the direction of each feature's effect i.e., whether it increases or decreases the likelihood of heart disease.

Local feature importance in decision trees explains how a single prediction was made by breaking it down feature by feature [6]. The explanation starts at the root of the tree, where the prediction is just the average outcome across all training samples (base prediction). As the

instance moves down the tree, each decision node splits the data based on a feature and updates the prediction. The change in prediction at each split (compared to the previous node) is attributed to the feature used for that split. By adding up these contributions along the path, we get a full, intuitive breakdown of how each feature influenced the final prediction.

	Feature	Δ Probability for Class 1
0	Chest Pain: Typical Angina	-0.2754
1	Fluoroscopy: 0 Vessels	0.2344
2	Exercise-Induced Angina: Yes	-0.2800
3	ST Depression Induced by Exercise	-0.1412
4	Resting Blood Pressure (mm Hg)	-0.0588

✓ Final predicted probability for Class 1: 0.0

Figure 12. Local feature attribution for a single prediction made by a decision tree model. The table shows how each feature influenced the predicted probability of heart disease for an individual instance.

To illustrate how local interpretation with decision trees works, let us consider the local interpretation of one instance shown in Figure 12. The base prediction for this model at the root was 52.1% probability of heart disease. As Figure 12 shows, the patient’s Typical Angina contributed -27.5 percentage points, reducing the probability to 24.6%. Then, Fluoroscopy: 0 Vessels increased the likelihood of disease by 23.4 points to 48.0%, but all other variables — Exercise-Induced Angina, ST Depression, and Resting Blood Pressure —decreased the prediction by a combined 48 percentage points, making the total sum 0, thus matching the predicted probability.

While decision trees are valued for their inherent interpretability, they come with notable limitations [9], [6], [99], [101]. Their primary limitation is that they quickly become overly complex when encountering intricate data, which can compromise their interpretability. To address these issues, pruning techniques are employed [101]: *pre-pruning* halts tree growth early based on predefined criteria such as maximum depth or minimum samples per node, while *post-pruning* simplifies an already fully grown tree by removing branches that offer little predictive value. Another weakness is that trees are not inherently monotonic, requiring extra cognitive effort to interpret decisions. Additionally, they do not accurately represent linear relationships. Similarly, they are unstable, as minor changes in training data can lead to entirely different structures. Finally, trees tend to overfit and therefore have limited generalization performance.

3.1.4.3 Rules-based systems

Logical models based on IF–THEN rules have existed since the 1970s, and many heuristics have since been developed to generate them [10]. Their long existence and structure make them intuitively interpretable [14], [6]. What distinguishes traditional from modern rule-based systems is that the latter are learned automatically from data through specialized algorithms, rather than being manually defined by programmers [6].

Rules-based systems offer many advantages in terms of interpretability. First of all, they mimic natural language reasoning by providing explicit decision-making processes, as they are based on a simple *IF-THEN* statement consisting of a condition and a predictor [6]. For example: *IF age > 50 AND smoker = 1 THEN cancer_risk = high*. This structure makes it very easy to examine which rules were used to reach a particular outcome. As a result, they are often used in medical diagnosis, legal decision-making, and financial regulation [101].

According to Molnar [6] their main benefit is that predictions are made fast, as only a “*few binary statements need to be checked to determine which rules apply*” [6]. He also notes that they are robust regarding monotonic transformations and outliers. On the other hand, Guidotti et al. [9] point out that, in contrast to the rigid and mutually exclusive paths of decision trees, decision rules offer a more flexible representation. To this, they add that decision rules do not capture insignificant clauses, which helps rules maintain interpretability and avoid overfitting on irrelevant patterns.

One of the most significant weaknesses of rules-based systems is that they can contain anything from a few simple rules to numerous complex rules [99]. Rudin [10] explains that this unnecessary impacts their sparsity and therefore interpretability, as some approaches produce many rules even when the same accuracy could be reached with fewer rules. She, however, notes that recent methods improve this weakness by optimizing both predictive performance and simplicity by minimizing two parameters: **i)** the fraction of misclassified training instances; and **ii)** the number of rules in the model.

Here are some of the more prominent examples of notable improvements to basic rule-based models:

- **Repeated Incremental Pruning to Produce Error Reduction (RIPPER)** [6] is based on the sequential covering approach, which incrementally learns one rule at a time to capture the structure of the training data. In each iteration, RIPPER constructs a rule

that aims to cover as many positive instances as possible while minimizing the coverage of negative ones. Once a rule is learned, the covered instances are removed from the training set, and the process repeats with the remaining data. This continues until most or all positive examples are covered. What sets RIPPER apart is its inclusion of a rule pruning phase that helps improve generalization and reduce overfitting.

- **Certiably Optimal Rule ListS (CORELS)** [10] unlike earlier brute-force methods, avoids exhaustive enumeration by employing theoretical bounds that prune large portions of the search space, along with a high-performance bit-vector library and clever data structures that reuse intermediate results and exploit symmetries in the rule construction process. These innovations enable CORELS to generate compact and optimally sparse rules efficiently, while maintaining both accuracy and interpretability.
- The **One Rule** [6] algorithm builds a simple, interpretable model by selecting the single best feature and creating one rule per unique value of that feature, assigning each the most frequent class label. To clarify, despite its name, the algorithm generates more than one rule, as it generates one rule for each value of a selected feature. As Molnar [6] puts it, the better name for the algorithm would be `OneFeatureRules`.
- **Falling Rule Lists (FRLs)** [14] consist of an ordered list of IF–THEN rules, where the predicted probability decreases monotonically as one moves down the list. This structure enhances interpretability by aligning with intuitive human reasoning: higher-risk conditions appear first, and each subsequent rule reflects a lower level of predicted risk. Unlike decision trees, which can be harder to follow due to branching complexity, FRLs enforce monotonicity and sparsity, yielding models that are both interpretable and compact, with only minimal sacrifices in accuracy.

Even with the cited improvements, there are still some deficiencies in decision rules-based systems [6], [101]. For one, they require categorical inputs, so continuous variables must be discretized, which reduces flexibility and leads to information loss. They also struggle to generalize beyond predefined rules, making them less effective in high-dimensional or complex datasets. Finally, they cannot capture smooth linear relationships and sometimes create conflicting rules, resulting in ambiguous outputs that require additional resolution logic.

To experiment with the interpretability of rules-based systems, we used a RIPPER-based model. In Figure 13, the local interpretation for instance number 0 is shown. Figure 13 illustrates that the rules generated by the basic code package are initially presented in a relatively raw format.

However, with a little bit of extra coding, we can extract a clear, human-intuitive version of the rules. When it comes to global interpretations, the systems display all the rules learned by the model, and coverage and feature importance can also be calculated, although this was not done as part of this thesis.

```

✔ Found instance with non-default rule at index #0
✔ True label: 1
✔ Predicted: True
📄 Matched rule (raw):
[Thalassemia:ReversibleDefect=1^Fluoroscopy:0^Vessels=1^ChestPain:TypicalAngina=0^STSlope:Flat=0]

📄 Matched rule (readable):
IF Thalassemia = Reversible Defect AND Fluoroscopy = 0 Vessels AND Chest Pain = Typical Angina AND ST Slope = Flat THEN Heart Disease = Yes

```

Figure 13. Example of a local explanation generated by a RIPPER-based rule model.

The figure shows both the raw and human-readable formats of the matched decision rule for instance #0. The rule predicts heart disease based on four factors: i) Thalassemia = Reversible Defect, ii) Fluoroscopy = 0 Vessels, iii) Chest Pain = Typical Angina, and iv) ST Slope = Flat. This example illustrates the interpretability advantage of rule-based systems, which provide clear logical conditions leading to prediction.

3.1.4.4 Interpretable neural networks

In this final subsection, we review three approaches that aim to make neural networks interpretable. These methods seek to retain the predictive power of neural networks while introducing structural constraints that enable interpretability.

One prominent approach is the Neural Additive Models (NAMs), which were proposed by Agarwal et al. [98]. NAMs are designed by placing restrictions on the structure of neural networks. Namely, NAMs work by assigning a separate neural network to each input feature, allowing the model to learn complex, non-linear relationships independently for each feature. These feature-specific networks are trained jointly, and their outputs are linearly combined to produce the final prediction. This results in inherently interpretable models, with a sacrifice of accuracy *vis-à-vis* neural networks, though the paper mentions that this applies to tabular data. Furthermore, NAMs show superior results compared to other interpretable models. Finally, NAM's feature-wise shape functions can be directly visualized, allowing decision-makers to see precisely how each input affects the prediction through simple, intuitive graphs.

Another interesting approach presented by Koh et al. [104] are the Concept Bottleneck Models (CBMs). Rather than predicting the output directly from raw inputs, CBMs decompose the task into two stages. In the first stage, a concept model g predicts a vector of human-understandable concepts (c) from the input data (x). For example, in the context of medical imaging, these concepts could include “bone spurs,” “calcification,” or “joint space narrowing.” In the second stage, a label model f predicts the final output y based solely on these predicted concepts, such

that the overall prediction function is defined as $y = f(g(x))$. The concept vector c serves as a semantic bottleneck. It forces the model's decision transformation into human-understandable concepts before the final prediction is made, thereby restricting reliance on uninterpretable raw features. This architecture is illustrated in Figure 14, which contrasts a standard end-to-end model with a CMB. This bottleneck structure enables users to inspect, reason about, and even intervene in the model's decisions. For example, suppose the model's prediction is based on the presence of calcification, but a clinician disagrees with that assessment. In that case, the clinician can change this category and observe how the output changes. A notable drawback of CBMs is their reliance on concept annotations during training, which can be both resource-intensive and domain-dependent.

Standard end-to-end model

$$x \rightarrow y$$

Concept Bottleneck Model

$$x \xrightarrow{g} c \xrightarrow{f} y$$

Figure 14. Comparison between a standard model and a Concept Bottleneck Model.

While in a standard end-to-end model, predictions are made directly from raw input data, in CMBs, the raw data is first used to predict values in a human-interpretable concept layer (c) (e.g., type of lesion, or color of an object). These predicted concepts then serve as input to a second model that makes the final prediction (e.g., disease diagnosis or object classification), enabling greater interpretability and potential for human intervention.

Finally, Chen et al. [105] propose the Prototypical Part Network (ProtoPNet) as an inherently interpretable neural network for visual classification tasks. The model is inspired by the reasoning process of human experts, who often make decisions by referencing familiar cases. Specifically, ProtoPNet classifies images by comparing parts of a new input image to a set of learned prototypical parts derived from the training data. As illustrated in Figure 15, the interpretations are offered with a combination of part-level attention by highlighting image regions that affect the decision and providing prototypical examples from the training set. This enables users to trace the model's reasoning back to concrete and understandable evidence. The model sacrificed about 3% in accuracy compared to a baseline black-box model, which is justified by considerable gains in interpretability.

Figure 15. Visual explanation generated by ProtoPNet.

The leftmost panel shows part-level attention, indicating the regions that most influenced the model's decision. The yellow box in the center image highlights the specific image patch that is compared to a learned prototype from the training set (right), forming the basis for the model's case-based reasoning.

Reproduced from Chen et al. This Looks Like That: Deep Learning for Interpretable Image Recognition, 2019 [105]

3.2 Using XAI tools to explain black box models

This subchapter serves as the focal point of the thesis, as it covers the key aspects of XAI techniques. In its core, explainability is based on generating simplified approximations of complex processes happening within the black box by basically building an inherently interpretable model that replicates, approximates, or mimics the behavior of the black box model [10], [30]. As they are simplified versions of reality, like other scientific models, such as those in physics, they sacrifice completeness for usability [106]. They are called *post hoc* because they are applied after the training of the underlying model and are decoupled from it [7], [11], [13], [16], [17], [6].

As a result, in AI Systems based on black boxes, two models are needed: **i)** a black box model that provides predictions, recommendations, decisions, and the like; and **ii)** an explanation model built on top of the black box that produces explanations. Both models' output is key for the user, as the user needs both a prediction to act and an explanation to trust. This parallel yet complementary coexistence of a black-box prediction model and a separate explanation-generating technique is illustrated in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Explainable machine learning pipeline.

It illustrates the parallel yet complementary roles of a black-box model and a separate explanation method. Reproduced from: Hsieh et al., *A Comprehensive Guide to Explainable AI: From Classical Models to LLMs*, 2024 [101].

3.2.1 Weaknesses of XAI techniques

“If the explanation was completely faithful to what the original model computes... one would not need the original model in the first place, only the explanation.” - Cynthia Rudin [10]

Post hoc techniques have been a subject of criticism due to issues related to:

- **Robustness** [27]: Explanations may vary unpredictably after small input changes, even when the outputs remain mostly the same.
- **Lack of fidelity** [10]: XAI techniques are at best an approximation of the underlying model. In some domains, XAI is not good enough even when the explanation model has a 90% fidelity, because this means that it is still incorrect 10% of the time. Even if explanations were entirely identical to the black box model, the explanation model could rely on different features to achieve the same result.
- **Lack of standardized frameworks for testing and verifying** [57]: Tests have been conducted by testing the XAI techniques on transparent models or by injecting artifacts. However, they introduce limitations such as reduced realism or artificial data bias.
- **Risk of automation bias** [57], [10], [12]: The phenomenon of *automation bias* arises when users place unwarranted trust in AI. It is applicable both for predictions and explanations. Studies show that explanations can increase over-reliance on them, creating a false sense of confidence, even when the explanations are nonsensical, incorrect, or misleading.

-
- **Undermining white box alternatives** [12]: The availability of seemingly reliable explanation techniques may discourage the usage of white box models, even though in many scenarios white box models work on par with black boxes.

The weaknesses above and the fact that there has been an explosion of new explainability techniques contribute to the ongoing debate of whether and which of the XIA techniques are sufficient to *justify moral or practical trust* in the black system [8].

3.2.2 Classifying XAI techniques

There are many frameworks that group explainability techniques, but the most common ones are based on: **i)** the level of explanations that the techniques provide; and **ii)** whether the technique can be applied to one or many models.

Based on the level of explanations that a technique provides, techniques can be divided into global and local XAI. *Global explanations* show how the model makes its decision overall, usually by aggregating individual instance explanations and offering an overview of the roles played by each feature and their relationships [15]. In broader terms, global explanations demonstrate how the black box makes predictions in general [11]. However, true global explanations are almost an impossible task due to human cognitive limitations that do not allow us to process more than a few parameters, as well as our inability to visualize more than three dimensions [11], [6]. Historically, more focus has been given to global models [106]. *Local explanations* explain why a black box model made a particular decision given a specific feature of the input [9], [15], [30]. Such explanations are a local approximation of how a black box works in one particular region [30]. Local interpretations are generally more achievable [6] and more accurate in the relevant data region than global explanations [100]. It must be underlined that the accuracy of local techniques is only relevant for a specific domain or ‘slice’ of a model, and therefore, the AI System provider must be very careful to point out these limitations in the system’s documentation [106], [30].

Based on their scope of application, XAI techniques can be grouped into model-specific and model-agnostic categories. *Model-specific techniques* are those that can be applied only to a specific type of model, such as neural networks [6]. On the other hand, *model-agnostic techniques* can be applied to any machine learning model [6]. For example, both on neural

networks and random forests. Due to scope limitations, we will cover only model agnostic approaches in this paper.

3.2.1 Benchmarks for explainability

There is a growing abundance of benchmarks that aim to define and evaluate the technical properties of XAI [107]. In this thesis, we will cover one recent and widely cited framework for evaluating and comparing XAI that is offered in the paper *From Anecdotal Evidence to Quantitative Evaluation Methods: A Systematic Review on Evaluating Explainable AI* [108]. It identifies twelve distinct properties that define what constitutes a *good* explanation in the context of XAI. The *Co-12 properties* are grouped into three main categories, but for estimating explainability from a technical aspect, only the “*content-oriented properties*” are relevant. They focus on the internal quality of the explanation itself. This group includes criteria six criteria, among which are: **i) correctness** - how faithful is the explanation to the black box’s behavior; **ii) completeness** - whether the explanation covers the full behavior of the model; **iii) consistency** - whether the explanations are stable across repeated runs for similar instances; **iv) continuity** - whether small changes in inputs result in small changes in the explanation; **v) contrastivity** - how well an explanation distinguishes why one output was produced instead of another; **vi) covariate complexity** - whether feature interactions or semantic dependencies in the explanation are understandable to humans. We will return to the other two groups of Co-12 properties in the Section 4.1.2 when we examine the benchmarks for human-friendly explanations.

Despite the abundance of explainability properties and benchmarks, Kadir et al. point out that a critical problem is that the frameworks do not provide quantitative measurements of the proposed benchmarks [107]. They note, however, that there is a growing field that develops quantitative measurements for explainability, especially regarding local explanations. Their work uncovers numerous approaches and offers a taxonomy of the emerging techniques. Therefore, it would be a valuable resource for a more detailed study on the development of standardized benchmarks in explainable AI.

3.2.2 Global explanation approaches

Global explanation techniques are designed to provide insights into how an AI model behaves across its entire input space, rather than for a single prediction. This section examines four widely adopted model-agnostic global explanation techniques: Partial Dependence Plots (PDP),

Accumulated Local Effects (ALE), Permutation Feature Importance (PFI), and Global Surrogate Models.

3.2.2.1 Partial Dependence Plot

Partial Dependence Plots (PDPs) are a model-agnostic and global post-hoc technique that provides a feature summary for each feature. They work by marginalizing the model's predictions over the joint distribution of the other features, effectively isolating the relationship between the features of interest and the predicted outcome [6], [30]. The explanation artifact they produce is a plot that visualizes the model's decision boundary as a function of a single feature, with the remaining features averaged out, thus showing the average effect of that feature on the model's outcome [99]. PDPs are very useful for understanding how a single feature affects the model's output [101].

According to Molnar [6], the key advantage of PDPs is their intuitive nature and the simple concept behind them, which makes them easy to understand even for non-technical stakeholders. He emphasizes that if the feature of interest is not correlated with other input features, then PDPs perfectly represent how the feature impacts the prediction on average. He explains that the theoretical definition of the partial dependence function is expressed as the expected value of the model's prediction, taken over the marginal distribution of other features.

Figure 17. Partial Dependence Plots that illustrate the marginal effect of a continuous (left) and a binary (right) feature.

In practice, creating PDPs involves three steps. To demonstrate this, we can take the left-side PDP depicted in Figure 17, which was developed as part of the experiment using the UCI Heart Disease dataset. In this case, a black box neural network was used to predict the probability of heart disease based on features such as Age, Exercise-Induced Angina, Max Heart Rate Achieved, and others. We aim to understand the global impact of Age, spanning from 29 to 77.

First, for each value of Age, a new dataset was created in which the Age feature is fixed at that specific value across all instances (for example, all rows have Age = 35). In contrast, all other features retained their original values. Second, each dataset was passed through the black model, and then the average prediction for that dataset was calculated. Finally, the average prediction for each dataset was plotted against the values of Age, producing the plot on the left side of Figure 17. The right-side plot in Figure 17 demonstrates that the method can also be used for binary variables.

The main limitation is that PDPs rely on the assumption that there is no correlation between the features, which is an unrealistic assumption in real-world data [6], [101]. This can obscure heterogeneous effects, as averaging across predictions may cancel out opposite effects in different data regions, falsely suggesting the feature has no impact [6], [99]. For example, analyzing the partial dependence of room count on house price without considering its correlation with total square meters may produce unrealistic scenarios (e.g., 8-room houses with only 40 m²). Human visual and conceptual capabilities impose another limitation, as you can present the relationship between two or a maximum of three features [6],[30]. Finally, PDPs can be computationally expensive for large or complex models and are less effective when applied to high-cardinality categorical features [101]. Even for the analysis of the variable Age in the UCI Heart Disease dataset, 48 new databases were created and passed through the black box model.

3.2.2.2 Accumulated Local Effects (ALE) Plot

Accumulated Local Effects (ALE) Plots are a global model-agnostic visualization technique. Unlike PDPs, ALE plots account for feature correlations by avoiding the independence assumption [6], [101]. ALE plots offer some additional benefits. They are more computationally efficient than PDPs, as *“for 20 grid points, PDPs require 20 times more predictions than the worst-case ALE plot”* [6].

The core idea behind ALE is to capture the local effect of a feature on the model’s prediction by computing the changes in predictions as the feature value is varied within a small grid of intervals [101]. The logic behind this approach is that by computing how the prediction changes when the feature is slightly increased, the method isolates the local effect of the feature while conditioning on the actual values of other features. These local differences are then *accumulated*

over the full range of the feature, producing a curve that represents the feature's overall effect on the prediction [6]

Figure 18. An Accumulated Local Effects Plot.

Illustrates the marginal effect of the continuous feature Age on the predicted probability of heart disease in the neural network model trained on the UCI Heart Disease dataset.

To illustrate how ALE is computed, let's analyze how the ALE plot depicted in Figure 18 was developed. We analyze the impact of the feature Age in the neural network trained on the UCI Heart Disease dataset. The ALE method divides the range of Age into intervals, such as [30–40), [40–50), etc. Firstly, two data sets are created, one where Age is fixed to the lower bound of an interval (e.g., 30) and one where it is fixed to the upper bound (e.g., 40), while all other features remain unchanged. Second, both the dataset with the lower bound and the one with the upper bound are run through the model. Third, the difference between the two predictions is computed for each instance. Finally, the difference is then averaged within the interval. With this, we have the local effect for one particular interval. This process is repeated for each interval, and the local effects accumulate to build the ALE plot.

ALE plots can also be done for two features by computing and accumulating local prediction differences over a grid of rectangular cells, then adjusting for the main effects of each feature to isolate and visualize only their interaction effect [6]. Still, ALE plots are not perfect. Some of their weaknesses are that: bad choices of intervals can obscure relevant effects, can suffer from overplotting in high-dimensional data, and can be computationally intensive for large datasets or complex models [101].

3.2.2.3 Permutation Feature Importance

Permutation Feature Importance (PFI) is a model-agnostic and global technique that evaluates the importance of a feature by measuring the increase in prediction error that results from randomly permuting its values. According to Molnar [6] PFI offers several advantages. First, it is straightforward to understand and interpret, yet it is a powerful way to understand global model behavior. Second, PFI is computationally efficient, as it does not require retraining the model, unlike alternative approaches that involve deleting a feature and fitting a new model. Finally, by evaluating how much a feature's permutation affects performance, the method naturally captures both main effects and interaction effects with other features.

This algorithm is probably the most straightforward to understand. The first step is to estimate the model's original error. The second step is to permute the feature of interest to break its relationship with the target variable. The third step is to run the permuted dataset through the model and obtain errors of the permuted model. Finally, the feature importance is then derived as a difference or quotient of the permuted dataset error and the original dataset error [6].

Figure 19. Top 5 features ranked by Permutation Feature Importance across three runs on a black box model. Taller bars indicate greater impact on model performance, as measured by increased log-loss when a feature is permuted. The procedure was repeated three times to assess stability, showing generally consistent rankings with some variation, particularly in the top feature.

As part of the thesis's experiment, the PFI procedure was performed three times on the experiment's black box neural network to assess the stability of the results. The results are presented in Figure 19, which depicts importance with a bar plot whereby the higher the bar, the bigger the error; therefore, the feature is more important. The ranking of the top features remained largely consistent across runs but is far from perfect. One concern is the fluctuations

regarding the top-ranked feature. One notable observation from the experiment is that the method proved to be highly computationally efficient, completing the three runs in a matter of seconds. This puts PFI in sharp contrast to other techniques. ICE plots, even when limited to a subset of instances, took significantly longer to compute, while SHAP-based global importance took almost twelve hours.

The notable limitations of PFI are: its reliance on random shuffling introduces variability across runs and creates implausible data points; its dependence on access to actual target values imposes usability limitations for many real-world problems; and it captures performance degradation, which may limit its suitability for particular interpretability objectives [6].

3.2.2.4 Global Surrogate

Global Surrogate models are another straightforward model-agnostic global technique. It involves training an interpretable model based on the input used by the black box and its corresponding outputs. According to Molnar [6] the unique advantage of this approach is that any white box model can be used as a surrogate, allowing organizations to tailor explanations to audiences' needs. He also notes that the explanation artefact of this XAI is a surrogate model that attempts to replicate the black-box model's decision function. He, however, cautions that before relying on the surrogate, its fidelity to the black box should be evaluated using metrics such as R^2 or MSE.

Figure 20. Top 5 features identified by a decision tree surrogate model.

The decision tree is used to approximate the predictions of a black box model. The surrogate achieved good fidelity ($R^2 = 0.813$), indicating it captured much of the black-box model's behavior despite its simplicity. One weakness is that it shares the same deficiency as the chosen explanation model (decision-tree) and lacks direction.

As part of the experiment, a couple of surrogates were trained based on the underlying neural network. In Figure 20, global explanations derived from a surrogate decision tree are presented. We test the fidelity as indicated by Molnar, and the results show an R^2 of 0.813 and an MSE of 0.037. This suggests that the tree captures the majority of the neural network's behavior. Unfortunately, the chosen surrogate model (decision tree) suffers from the same weaknesses of global interpretation of decision trees listed in Subsection 3.1.4.2. Namely, the plot in Figure 20 does not indicate the direction of each feature's contribution to the model's predictions. This illustrates that a surrogate model comes with all the advantages, disadvantages, and interpretation challenges that come with that type of model [6].

3.2.3 Local explanation approaches

While global explanation methods aim to provide insights into the overall behavior of an AI model, local explanation techniques focus on interpreting individual predictions. This section examines five widely recognized local model-agnostic explanation methods: Individual Conditional Expectation (ICE), Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME), Anchors, Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP), and Counterfactual Explanations.

3.2.3.1 Individual Conditional Expectation (ICE)

Individual Conditional Expectation (ICE) plots are a local model-agnostic XAI that produces visualizations. ICE plots provide a granular view by displaying one curve per instance, illustrating how the prediction for that observation changes as the value of the interest varies, which makes them especially good for identifying heterogeneous effects [6], [101], [2].

The paper *A Comprehensive Guide to Explainable AI: From Classical Models to LLMs* [101] notes some of the essential limitations of ICE plots. For one, they assume that features are independent, which means they may sometimes represent implausible data combinations. Additionally, ICE plots can be affected by overplotting in large datasets, making visual interpretation challenging. Finally, ICE can be computationally demanding when applied to complex models or data.

As part of the experiment, ICE was applied to the black-box model. However, generating ICE plots proved to be prohibitively computationally intensive, especially when scaling to a larger subset of instances. Due to these limitations, the analysis was restricted to only 20 instances.

This constraint likely contributed to the inability to produce visualizations that offer meaningful insights. Consequently, no ICE visualizations are presented in this thesis.

3.2.3.2 Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanation

Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanation (LIME) is a model-agnostic and local explanation approach that provides an explanation of individual predictions by building simpler models based on the local approximation of the complex model [109], [9]. LIME, along with SHAP, have been consistently cited as the most relevant explanation techniques [99], [109].

LIME's most significant advantage is that it is adaptable to a wide range of data types (tabular, image, text) and works with all sorts of traditional and modern AI models [6]. Also, its results can be easily visualized [109], [110]. The authors of LIME [110] claim that it is effective in helping users assess the trustworthiness of individual AI predictions, as it maintains high precision and recall in identifying predictions that remain stable even when untrustworthy features are removed. This indicates that its explanations reliably reflect robust model behavior. One key advantage of LIME is noted by Dieber and Kirrane [111] is that LIME is an open source tool with plentiful publicly available materials to guide implementation.

$$\text{explanation}(x) = \arg \min_{g \in G} L(f, g, \pi_x) + \Omega(g)$$

Figure 21. LIME optimization formula that minimizes local loss around instance x and penalizes complexity through regularization term $\Omega(g)$

The equation in Figure 21 shows that with LIME, the local interpretation of data instance x is obtained by finding an interpretable model $g \in G$, where G is the set of all possible interpretable models. The optimization objective has two parts: **(i)** it minimizes the loss function $L(f, g, \pi_x)$, which quantifies how well the interpretable model g approximates the predictions of the black-box model f in the neighborhood of x , with proximity weighted by the kernel π_x ; and **(ii)** it penalizes the complexity of g through the regularization term $\Omega(g)$ thereby contributing to sparser explanation. This optimization aims to strike a balance between fidelity and complexity.

Multiple authors [30], [6] including Ribeiro et al. [110] – the original proposers of LIME – explain how the method works in practice. First, instance x is chosen for explanation. Second, a new synthetic data set is created by perturbing the data of instance x . Third, the synthetic dataset is run via the black box model to generate predictions. Fourth, a kernel π_x is used to

produce weights for the loss function based on the distance between the original instance x and the perturbed instances. The weights are used so that the surrogate model g better approximates the black-box model f near the original instance x . Finally, model g is developed that minimizes: **i)** the loss between the predictions of the original model f and interpretable model g , usually with weighted square error; and **ii)** the complexity of the interpretable model g , regulated with the parameter λ , whereby a small λ produced a model g that yields more accurate predictions, but is potentially harder to interpret and a big λ produced a sparser model, which might be less accurate.

In the experiment, LIME was initially tested with 1,000 perturbed samples, which were used to create the surrogate model and the library's default kernel width. The results of three runs for Instance 40, visualized in Figure 22, demonstrates a high level of volatility as all three results differ from one another.

Figure 22. LIME stability test for one instance.

Bar plots from three independent LIME runs reveal inconsistent feature attributions despite identical prediction probabilities for Feature 40, illustrating the method's sensitivity to perturbation and highlighting its instability.

To improve the stability of the explanations, systematic hyperparameter tuning was conducted over two critical settings: **i)** perturbation sample size (1,000, 2,000, 5,000); and **ii)** kernel width (2.65, 5.29, 10.58). For each configuration, 50 explanations were generated for the same instance. Then the average standard deviation of the top 5 feature weights across runs (σ) was computed to quantify volatility, and the per-call runtime was measured to capture computational cost. The goal is to identify the sweet spot that minimizes explanation variance without incurring prohibitive delays.

The results of this process are presented in Figure 23, which demonstrates that the volatility of the explanation steadily decreases as the LIME sample size increases, and the kernel width is tightened. The most stable configuration was 5,000 samples with the narrowest kernel (2.65), which reduced volatility by approximately 20% compared to the 2,000-sample configuration

with the same kernel, at the cost of only about one additional second per explanation. However, this is not necessarily the sweet spot because explanations can degenerate as the kernel nears zero and can yield unfaithful or completely disconnected explanations [112]. To avoid this, we chose the wider kernel (10.58). In addition, the wider kernel, although slightly less stable, still achieves nearly comparable volatility while being marginally faster than the narrow kernel, but slower by approximately 40% compared to LIME, which uses 2000 samples and a wide kernel.

Figure 23. Effect of LIME sample size and kernel width on explanation stability and runtime. The left plot shows that increasing the number of perturbed samples improves stability (lower standard deviation of top feature weights), particularly with narrower kernels. The right plot shows that greater sample sizes lead to longer runtimes per explanation, with only minor differences across kernel widths.

While this trade-off is acceptable for occasional analyses, it may not scale well if the system must generate hundreds or thousands of explanations concurrently. In those cases, even a one-second overhead per call could become prohibitive. However, there might be room for more optimization if the LIME explanation were built on 3,000 or 4,000 samples. Even without further testing, the experiment demonstrates that LIME is significantly faster than SHAP, as confirmed in the chapter on SHAP. Finally, it should be noted that the optimization did yield more stable predictions; however, instability persisted. Namely, out of the five runs conducted to test the optimization, three runs showed almost identical feature importance. In comparison, two runs differed in terms of both the direction and magnitude of some features. This behavior demonstrates LIME’s main weakness: a lack of faithfulness to the underlying model [98].

Leaving the example behind, LIME can also be used for analyzing textual data and image data. Molnar explains [6] that LIME creates perturbed data points by randomly removing words from the original text. Each perturbed version is then represented as a binary vector, where each feature indicates whether a specific word is present (1) or absent (0). This enables the identification of which individual words contribute most to the model’s decision. He also

explains how LIME works for image data. Namely, LIME does not perturb single pixels. Instead, it segments the image into superpixels (groups of similar, connected pixels) and creates perturbed versions by turning superpixels off, typically by replacing them with a color like gray. The resulting predictions are used to fit a local linear model that highlights regions where the probability of the predicted class increases or decreases. Figure 24 illustrates this process, showing how LIME generates interpretable image explanations through segmentation, perturbation, and local surrogate modeling.

Figure 24. Illustration of the LIME process for explaining image classification. The figure illustrates how LIME approximates the local decision boundary of a black-box model by analyzing how different superpixel combinations affect the prediction. This process enables the identification of image regions that contribute most significantly to the model's output.

Adapted from Arteaga [113], Interpretable Machine Learning for Image Classification with LIME

Regarding limitations, as the experiment demonstrates, the biggest downside is its instability. This makes it hard to trust the results [6]. Additionally, as the experiment demonstrates and Molnar notes [6], defining the local neighborhood (i.e., the width of the kernel) is a guessing game or trial and error. In addition, as LIME perturbs data without considering feature correlations, it often produces unrealistic instances and can be misleading in the presence of collinearity [6], [109]. As a result of these weaknesses, LIME might not be the right XAI tool for domains where stability and fidelity are crucial. Finally, it should be noted that the authors of LIME [110] also propose SP-LIME (Submodular Pick for LIME) as a method to provide a global explanations. They also present the findings of experiments that demonstrate the usability and reliability of SP-LIME. However, SP-LIME is not often cited as a global explanation technique.

3.2.3.3 Scoped Rules (Anchors)

Scoped Rules (Anchors) provide local explanations by identifying simple, human-readable if-then rules called “anchor”. Molnar [6] explains that the rules are locally precise, which means that when the anchor conditions are met, the model almost always gives the same output. The authors of Anchors [114] – that interestingly enough are also authors of LIME – note that rules created with Anchors capture the impactful features, while leaving out the rest, resulting in sparse explanations. They note that the most significant advantage of the Anchors is that they provide clear and explicit coverage, meaning the explanation only applies when all conditions in the rule are satisfied. They contrast this with LIME, where unclear coverage can mislead users into overgeneralizing explanations to instances where they do not hold, reducing human precision.

A couple of works can be used to reconstruct how Anchors work in practice [9], [6], [114]. Suppose we have a model that predicts whether a customer will purchase a product, and we want to explain a specific case where Age = 40, Gender = M, and Income = High, with the model predicting a purchase. First, a simple rule is created using one feature (ex: Gender = M). The algorithm then generates a synthetic dataset by fixing this feature and randomly perturbing the others (Age and Income). These perturbed instances are passed through the black-box model. If the model still predicts “purchase” in 75% of cases, the precision of the rule is 0.75. This is repeated for all single-feature rules, which are then ranked by precision. If none meet the desired threshold (usually 95%) [114], the top candidate rules are expanded by adding another feature (e.g., Gender = M AND Income = High), and a new perturbed dataset is created

with both features fixed. The process of expanding and testing continues until a rule meets the threshold. Unfortunately, due to limited skills it was challenging to implement Anchors, and after some tries, it was decided that for this XAI, it is not possible to conduct the experiment.

To be clear, it would be computationally infeasible to test all possible combinations of features. To make the computation feasible, Anchors proceed not by testing all possible combinations, but use optimization techniques such as [6], [114]: **i)** *the KL-LUCB multiarmed bandit strategy* to efficiently identify the best candidate rule by allocating sampling resources to estimate precision with high confidence and minimal model queries; and **ii)** *Beam-Search* that retains only a fixed number of top-performing candidate rules at each step and iteratively expands them, ensuring tractable exploration of the most promising rule combinations. Molnar [6] notes that even with these algorithmic strategies, Anchor requires numerous calls to the underlying black-box model, resulting in high runtime and computational demands. He identifies another issue: linear features must be discretized, which leads to information loss and poor discretization decisions.

3.2.3.4 Shapley additive explanations (SHAP)

Shapley additive explanations (SHAP) is the most consistent and theoretically grounded model-agnostic approach that can be used to provide *both local and global explanations* [101], [109]. It builds on the theoretical foundations of Shapley Values to add efficiency and global interpretation [16]. Molnar explains [6] that Shapley values are a concept from cooperative game theory used to fairly distribute a total payoff among players based on their individual contributions to all possible coalitions. In machine learning, they measure how much each feature contributes to a model's prediction by averaging its marginal impact across all possible subsets of features. According to him, the key innovation of SHAP is to represent "*Shapley value explanation... as an additive feature attribution method, a linear model...*" [6]. There are model-specific SHAP approaches, such as MaxSHAP, TreeSHAP, DeepSHAP, or LinearSHAP [6],[16]. However, here the focus is on Kernel SHAP, a model-agnostic approach. It offers computational efficiency advantages for computing Shapley values, since instead of relying on the spectrum of possible subsets of features, it uses sampled subsets.

Let's proceed with a reconstruction of how Kernel SHAP works in practice [6], [16]. In the first step, coalitions are sampled from the whole spectrum of feature subsets. Priority is given to the smallest and largest coalitions as the most informative. Namely, "*we start with all possible*

coalitions with 1 and $M-1$ features, which makes 2 times M coalitions in total... [and depending on computation budget] we can include coalitions with two features and with $M-2$ features and so on” [6]. In the second step, SHAP runs the predictions for each sampled coalition through the black box. Features not included in the coalition are sampled by marginal distribution, which unfortunately ignores dependencies between features and creates the issue that is common in permutation-based XAI [6]. In step three, SHAP assigns weights to the sampled instances, whereby small and large coalitions are allotted larger weights. Intuitively, from single-feature coalitions we learn about the isolated effects of a feature, while from large coalitions we learn about the total effect. At this point, all the ingredients are present to fit a linear surrogate model [99]. In this model, the Shapley values correspond to the coefficients (or weights) of the linear model, just as in standard linear regression. The final step is to fit the explanation model by minimizing the weighted squared error loss shown on the right.

For the experiment, SHAP was tested out both as a local and a global XAI technique. For local explanation, for instance #40, the bar plot presented in Figure 25 was produced. It displays the top 8 features with the highest SHAP values, indicating their strength and direction. Another visualization technique for local interpretations was tried out.

Figure 25. The top 8 features that contribute most to a prediction for one instance, based on absolute SHAP values. This plot shows the local importance of the top eight features that impacted the prediction for Instance 40.

In addition, the *force plot* shown in Figure 26 illustrates the full SHAP breakdown, for instance 0, demonstrating how each feature contributes to pushing the prediction from the base value (≈ 0.55) toward the final output (≈ 0.74). Features in red increase the prediction, while those in blue decrease it. Evidently, *showing all the features may make the force plot too crowded for straightforward interpretation.*

Figure 26. SHAP force plot for Instance 40 showing how each feature contributes to shifting the model's prediction from the base value (~ 0.55) to the final output probability of 0.74. Red features increase the prediction, while blue features decrease it.

In addition to testing the explanation artefacts, an experiment was also conducted to test the stability of Kernel SHAP by performing five explanation runs for instance #40. The line plot presented in Figure 27 shows the SHAP Values for the top 5 features across runs. It reveals that the values remain highly consistent with minimal variation, which proves that Kernel SHAP provides stable and reliable local explanations. Despite this impressive result, it is worth noting that even explaining a single instance on a toy dataset took between 84 and 88 seconds.

Figure 27. SHAP values across five explanation runs for the same instance. Presents the SHAP values across five runs for Instance 40, showing consistent attributions for the top 5 features. The minimal variation across runs demonstrates the high stability of Kernel SHAP.

A final aspect of the experiment was testing Kernel SHAP for global explainability. The first step was to generate local explanations for all the testing data instances (260 rows). Then, these local explanations were converted into a global explanation by summing up the absolute Shapley values for each feature across the locally explained instances. To visualize global importance, the *SHAP summary plot* shown in Figure 28 was used. Each point represents a SHAP value for a feature in a given instance, and the color represents the actual feature value from low to high [6].

Figure 28. SHAP summary plot showing the top 10 features influencing model predictions globally, with color indicating feature value and direction indicating impact.

As a final remark on the experiment with SHAP as a global XAI technique, it is worth noting that it took 9 hours, 25 minutes, and 12 seconds to calculate all the SHAP values, despite the simplicity of the dataset. This proves that, despite efficiency gains, compared to traditional ways of calculating Shapley Values, Kernel SHAP is still computationally demanding [6]. Another key weakness is that Kernel SHAP assumes feature independence, which can lead to unrealistic data instances, affecting the quality of the attributions [99], [109], [6].

Despite its weaknesses, SHAP remains unique among explanation techniques because it fulfills three crucial properties [16]: **i) local accuracy**, which ensures the explanation model's output matches the original model's prediction for the given input; **ii) missingness**, which assigns zero attribution to any absent feature; and **iii) consistency**, which guarantees that if a model changes to increase a feature's contribution, its attribution does not decrease. These properties make SHAP the only method that provides fair and theoretically sound additive explanations and is computationally feasible [16], [6].

The discussion on SHAP should be closed by noting that it has attracted a lot of attention in the XAI community, and as a result, there are many efforts to address its limitations or extend its functionality [99]: **i)** Kumar et al. introduced diagnostic tools to help interpret SHAP values more reliably; **ii)** Joseph proposed statistical tests to generate confidence intervals for Shapley values; **iii)** Song et al., used Shapley values to quantify variable importance as an alternative to functional ANOVA.

3.2.3.5 Counterfactual Explanations

Counterfactual explanations are part of a distinct class of interpretability methods, known as example-based explanations. They aim to detect the slightest change of a feature value that leads to a change in prediction [6]. To be reliable and usable, the counterfactual should [6], [115]: **i)** be as similar as possible to the instance; **ii)** change as few features as possible; **iii)** generate multiple diverse counterfactual explanations; and **iv)** have likely feature values. The last point is critical since some features might not be changeable, such as race. To satisfy the requirement from point iii, Mothilal et al. [115] have proposed the *Diverse Counterfactual Explanations (DiCE)*, which generates examples that are actionable and diverse.

Counterfactuals are a desired XAI method because they provide the opportunity to explore causality by examining what changes in the input would lead to a different outcome [2], [30]. Thus, they provide “what-if” information by showing how the model would react if the data was changed [30]. Furthermore, this method is more intuitively understandable than methods that depend on decision boundaries, [30] like the Anchors method.

Molnar [6] provides details of two methods for obtaining counterfactual explanations. The first one is the *Wachter et al.* It aims to minimize: **i)** the model’s prediction for the counterfactual x' -instance and the desired outcome y' , predefined by the user; and **ii)** the distance between the original x -instance and the counterfactual x' -instance. However, this method has two key weaknesses. First, it does not minimize the number of changed features. Additionally, it is computationally demanding when handling categorical features with numerous distinct levels. The other Method that Molnar covers is the method by Dandl et al., which has four objectives instead of two. In addition to minimizing the distance between x and x' (objective o_2), and difference between the counterfactual output $f(x')$ and the desired y' (objective o_1), this method also: **i)** counts the number of features changed to enable sparsity (objective o_3); and **ii)** reflects the need for the counterfactuals to be built by likely features values and combinations (objective o_4).

The counterfactual generation methods could not be successfully implemented despite multiple attempts due to technical and computational challenges; therefore, no experimental results are presented in this section.

3.3 Closing the chapter on explainability in a technological context

This chapter has outlined the two principal technical pathways for meeting the explainability standards of the AI Act: **i)** relying on inherently interpretable models, and **ii)** implementing post hoc explainability techniques for black-box models.

Inherently interpretable models, also known as white-box models, are a viable and underappreciated strategy for avoiding the need to implement explainability standards altogether. Linear regression, decision trees, rule-based systems, and more advanced constructs such as Generalized Additive Models (GAMs) or interpretable neural networks enable direct insight into the logic behind predictions. However, as shown throughout this chapter, their simplicity comes at the cost of reduced flexibility, potential limitations in accuracy, and difficulties in modeling complex relationships. Furthermore, even white-box models experience reduced interpretability as the number of features increases or the relationships between variables become unintuitive.

By contrast, post hoc explainability techniques, collectively referred to as XAI, aim to make black-box models more transparent after training. Techniques vary depending on their scope of applicability (model-agnostic versus model-specific approaches), as well as whether they can provide local, global, or both types of explanations. The literature review and the experiments show that each technique has its positive and negative aspects. One notable aspect revealed by the experiment is the *trade-off between reliability and speed*, which is also mentioned in the literature [116]. This trade-off arises when selecting among various techniques, as illustrated by the comparison between LIME and Kernel SHAP. However, a trade-off also exists between different implementations of the same method, as demonstrated by experimentation with LIME. Therefore, a key takeaway is that organizations must be capable of experimenting with various techniques and implementations to find the best approach for their AI System and their context.

One overarching problem for both inherently interpretable models and post-hoc explainability techniques is the lack of consensus on how to evaluate them. The thesis chapter presents numerous criteria but also highlights that there is little agreement on which are most important, how they should be prioritized, or how they should be measured in practice. Crucially, there is currently a lack of quantifiable metrics for the proposed criteria; however, this is changing rapidly as the topic attracts increasing attention. This hampers comparability between different

methods and creates challenges for organizations seeking to select, validate, or defend their explainability strategies.

4 Explainability in the organizational context

A recent global survey by Altair identifies the key sources of “friction” that hinder the successful implementation of AI projects. Among the most common barriers are: “*the difficulty in finding qualified data science talent, low levels of AI literacy across the workforce, the need to invest time and resources in existing upskilling staff, overly complex AI tool design, outdated legacy systems, and financial constraints*” [117]. These findings suggest that implementing AI, and by extension, XAI projects, depend on tackling both organizational and technical challenges. As a matter of fact, Interviewee 2 noted, and the literature review will show, organizational challenges are much less well defined and preclude organizations from using even the technology that is widely available.

The following subchapters examine a selection of organizational challenges that are either cited in the existing literature, are based on findings from the experiment, or are derived from interviews with experts. One general note is that interest in XAI, beyond its algorithmic aspects, is relatively recent. Therefore, there is a limited body of academic research specifically addressing organizational dimensions of XAI. This has two implications. First, the analysis draws more heavily on insights from reports, publications by standardization bodies, and consultancy studies. Second, the analysis to some extent relies on analogy, applying general knowledge about AI to the specific context of XAI.

4.1 Defining and evaluating explanations

One of the most discussed challenges of XAI is defining *what constitutes a "good" explanation*. The answer depends on a complex interplay of technical, ethical, legal, psychological, and philosophical factors that researchers are only beginning to unravel.

4.1.1 Navigating trade-offs: When to use which approach?

Chapter 2 highlighted a widely recognized *trade-off between explainability and other principles of trustworthy AI*. Chapter 3 noted the *trade-off between the speed and reliability of the explanation*. In addition to trade-offs, organizations need to navigate choices among an ever-expanding array of XAI techniques [118]. While professional bodies such as Deloitte [119] and

a growing body of academic literature [118], [116], [106] provide some guidance on these issues, recommendations remain high-level and lack actionable specificity for particular applications.

This thesis argues that the trade-offs and model choices cannot be effectively resolved at the domain level (e.g., healthcare). Interviewee 1 revealed an interesting perspective from experiences with the need in the healthcare domain. For example, an AI system used for triaging patient referrals may allow for more flexible or simplified explanations. At the same time, diagnostics tools demand a significantly higher standard of explainability and allow for processing time. Then again, in urgent clinical situations, even high-stakes decision support tools cannot rely on explanations that take too long to generate. This is why *trade-offs must be carefully weighed and decided upon at the level of individual use cases*. Developing a comprehensive, one-size-fits-all framework is a herculean task, given the vast number of domains, each encompassing hundreds, if not thousands, of distinct use cases with their contextual requirements and risk profiles. However, *developing sector-specific or industry-level frameworks is both feasible and necessary*.

4.1.2 Human-centered benchmarks and principles for explainability

Miller [120] notes that traditionally, explainability techniques have been developed in the context of a phenomenon known as "Inmates Running the Asylum". He borrows this concept from earlier works that criticize software as often being poorly designed from a user's perspective, because programmers are in charge of design decisions rather than interaction designers. Miller argues that history is repeating itself in the field of XAI, as AI researchers are developing XAI for their own use. He elaborates that insights from the social sciences, such as philosophy and psychology, which have been accumulating for centuries, are ignored. This mismatch between the technical and sociological sides of XAI became especially apparent in the 2020s, as the realization emerged that *"to achieve AI transparency for end users, capabilities from computer science have to be accompanied by insights from social science"* [17]. As a result, in the past few years, researchers have put effort into building bridges between the fields of AI, Human-Computer Interaction, and Social Sciences [20]. Notable examples of such works are: Explaining Explanations in AI [106], Expanding Explainability: Towards Social Transparency in AI systems [121], Human-centered Explainable AI: Towards a Reflective Sociotechnical Approach [122], Explanation in Artificial Intelligence: Insights from the Social Sciences [20], and other works.

The growing interest in the field has been followed by the development of several human-centered interpretability principles [6], [106]. Here we will focus on one very coherent set of benchmarks for human-friendly explanations - the *Co-12 Properties* [108], first introduced in Section 3.2.1. In that section, we covered the content-oriented group of properties relevant for the technical quality of explanations. Here, we will cover the two other groups that focus on the qualities of explanations from the user's perspective. The first group, **Presentation-Oriented Properties**, addresses how the explanation is structured and conveyed. It includes tree properties, among which are: **i) compactness** - refers to the size and cognitive load of the explanation, favoring the “less is more” principle; **ii) composition** - concerns the format and logical organization of the explanation, which can affect user clarity; and **iii) confidence** - evaluates whether the explanation includes a measure of certainty (e.g., probabilistic confidence scores). The second group, **User-Relevant Properties**, focuses on the usability of the explanation from the perspective of the end user: **i) context** - how well the explanation aligns with the needs, goals, and expertise of the target audience; **ii) coherence** – measures whether the explanation aligns with the user's prior knowledge or beliefs; and **iii) controllability** - addresses whether users can interact with the explanation, ask “what-if” questions, or influence how it is delivered.

4.1.3 The Role of Stakeholders in Shaping Explainability: From Theory to Standardization

One reason it is challenging to produce a formal and all-purpose definition of what constitutes a good explanation is that the answer is highly subjective and domain- and context-dependent [2], [11], [9]. Diverse groups of stakeholders, including lawyers, philosophers, and ML specialists, all agree on the general importance of XAI, but struggle to define what this means in practice [106]. Additionally, there is a conflict between faithfulness and comprehensibility, as detailed explanations may be too complex for users to understand, while simple explanations may misrepresent the model's logic [57]. Therefore, a good explanation is dependent on the specific needs of the stakeholders and the application scenario [22]. Interviewee 2 emphasized that to understand the particular needs of the stakeholder, it is beneficial to encourage the user organization to develop data science internal talent that will be involved in the daily operations to be a bridge between the provider and the deployer.

The *IEEE 7001-2021* [35] standard provides a structured, stakeholder-based framework. Its focus is on the broader category of transparency, where explainability and interpretability are

key components. It lists *five stakeholder groups: users of autonomous systems, the general public and bystanders, validation and certification bodies, incident investigators, and expert advisors in legal and administrative contexts*. For each group, there are three subtypes of users (non-expert, expert, and super users). For this paper, the stakeholder group of autonomous system users is relevant, with the focus on the particular expert subgroup. They correspond to deployers under the AI Act, for which provider must develop interfaces to follow and understand AI Systems and their decisions. The expectations of transparency, which also include explainability and interpretability, are categorized into six levels of openness, ranging from Level 0 (no transparency) to Level 5 (maximum openness). Each level is accompanied by varying degrees of accessible information, interactivity, and adaptability. The key points are:

- **Level 1** - requires documentation that explains the system’s general principles of operation and shows expected behavior. Though this does not necessitate dynamic explanation interfaces, it still implies including some artefacts that are developed with global or counterfactual techniques.
- **Level 3** - the systems must provide on-demand explanations. They should be delivered in domain-appropriate language to ensure they are understandable and actionable in the relevant context. This level marks a transition from passive transparency to interactive, user-driven explainability.
- **Level 4** - the system needs to allow the user to explore hypothetical “what if” scenarios. This level represents a more advanced form of explainability, where users are not only informed but actively engaged in exploring the system’s decision logic
- **Level 5** - the system must provide a continuous, adaptive explanation of its behavior, tailored to the user’s context and information needs. Domain experts need to be supported with rich, context-sensitive artefacts.

4.1.4 Choosing the right elements of an explanation

When it comes to designing proper explanation artifacts, the *NISTIR 8312: Four Principles of Explainable AI* [95] introduces a framework of thinking about the quality of explanations, visualized with Figure 29, based on: **i) purpose** - why the explanation is requested; and **ii) style** - how it is delivered. Both purpose and style are influenced by the individual’s role in or around the system. The standard does not provide much guidance on purpose, as purpose defies definition and must be assessed in every particular case. It gives more detail when defining an explanation style. Explanation style is based on *three key elements*. The first element is the *level*

of detail, which ranges from brief messages to extensive reports. Then the second element is *interaction type* and comes in three forms, such as: declarative explanations based on predefined queries that the recipient cannot alter (most common approach); one-way interaction, where the explanation is determined based on a query issued by the recipient and allows the user to probe the system; and two-way interaction would allow the person to probe the system, while the machine can prove back by asking clarifying questions or propose different approaches to exploration. The final element that defines style is *the explanation format*. It may include various visual and graphical elements, verbal and auditory components, or even visual alerts, such as alarms, flashing lights, and other similar elements. This is highly dependent on the purpose. For example, a warning system would contain much less information that would be delivered abruptly, in comparison to an explanation of a specific diagnosis.

Figure 29. Explanation styles in AI systems, as defined by NISTIR 8312.

The figure illustrates three key elements of explanation style: i) level of detail, ranging from sparse to extensive explanations; ii) degree of interaction, spanning from declarative (system-initiated), to one-way (user-initiated), to two-way (interactive dialogue); and iii) format, which can include graphical/visual components, verbal (written or auditory) communication, and visual/auditory alerts.

Reproduced from NISTIR 8312: Four Principles of Explainable Artificial Intelligence, 2021 [95].

4.1.5 Designing and evaluating explanation interfaces

When designing explanation interfaces, it is crucial to understand that human explanations draw upon personal experiences, background knowledge, and intuition and may be shaped by cultural, historical, or individual factors [2]. In addition, laypersons do not easily distinguish between global and local explanations and other factors that may influence transparency in their

specific purpose or context [17]. Furthermore, prior experiences with similar systems shape the users' attitudes toward the explanation interface [17]. Another insight is that a user's need is also dependent on their experience in their domain, so novices require more explanations than experts [15].

In some cases, the explanation can pose more of a problem than a solution. According to Mittelstadt et al., [106] if the user does not understand the boundaries of reliability of an explanation system, then the explanation can become misleading and offer a false sense of transparency. According to them, this is particularly true for local explanations, as non-expert users may be unaware of the limitations of the explanation and mistakenly believe it applies more broadly than it does. They note that this creates a serious risk for users to overlook the complexities, interactions, or nonlinearities present in the complete model.

The situation is exacerbated by the tendency of users to overly rely on automatically made decisions, even if this means that the decision goes against the user's own opinion or when explanations are nonsensical; a phenomenon known as *automation bias* [15], [109], [123], [21]. Studies show that novice users are particularly vulnerable to automation bias, but some studies suggest that experts are also susceptible [109]. That is why information should also be provided by detailing the limitations of a system [106]. But according to Wang et al. [124], automation bias is not the only cognitive bias affecting AI-assisted decisions. Other biases include representativeness bias (judging a case by similarity to others), which can be mitigated by showing prototype cases and feature contrasts; availability bias (overestimating likely outcomes), addressed by displaying base rates from the training data; anchoring bias (fixating too early on one explanation), mitigated through counterfactuals and premortem analysis; and confirmation bias (favoring evidence that supports initial beliefs), reduced by showing input attributions before system predictions. However, they note that these four biases represent only a small subset of a much *larger pool of over 50 known cognitive biases*.

The complexity of these matters on a theoretical level is compounded by the fact that designers cannot understand these issues on their own. Therefore, users' involvement in the design and evaluation phases is highly recommended to uncover the aspects of the system that are sensitive or not immediately apparent to developers [17]. Early involvement of relevant stakeholders can help avoid downstream conflicts between "engineers" and "explainers" [125] and the explanation interface should be rigorously tested and thoroughly validated [106]. Interviewee 2 noted that his approach when offering solutions to clients is to spend time not with the

management, but with the end users to understand how they make decisions. To paraphrase him, you should ask potential users, “what do you need to see to have peace of mind”?

To facilitate better XAI-user interactions, recent work has emphasized the importance of *advisability*, which advocates for incorporating user feedback to improve explanation artifacts [119]. A related concept is the *co-design* of human-centered XAI systems. For example, Panigutti et al. [126] argue that the development of explainable AI systems consists of two distinct phases. They concede that the first phase, designing the technical method for extracting explanations from black-box models, is too specialized for end-user participation. However, they emphasize that in the second phase, developing the explanation interface, users should be actively involved, not merely as passive recipients of explanations, but as co-designers. The authors propose an iterative cycle in which user feedback is used to “*discover new requirements for the explanation, which is then redesigned to fulfill those requirements and re-evaluated*” [126]. Another co-design framework is proposed by Lee et al. through their AI Design Explanation Card (*AI-DEC*) method [127]. This framework introduces a card-based design tool structured around four key communication dimensions: content, modality, frequency, and direction. The AI-DEC cards are used in participatory co-design sessions with end-users to prototype explanation interfaces that reflect their contextual needs and values.

Finally, one remarkably straightforward and holistic framework for assessing XAI implementations is offered by Dieber and Kirrane [111]. Their Model Usability Evaluation (MUSE) was developed for testing LIME explanations but can be broadly applied to any XAI method. The framework includes three dimensions to evaluate explanation techniques. The first is the *effectiveness of explanations*, which considers how complete and understandable the explanations are (both at the local and global level) and examines the potential risks and consequences of users misinterpreting the information. The second dimension is *user satisfaction*, which evaluates the user's overall experience with the explanation tool, including whether the interaction evokes positive or negative emotions, the level of confidence users feel, and how satisfying they perceive the final output to be. What makes this framework holistic is that it includes a component for assessing *resource requirements* for implementing and using the technique. Namely, it evaluates the time, effort, and cognitive load involved, asking whether the process is efficient, what additional costs are incurred, and whether the interaction leads to user fatigue.

4.2 Resource constraints, governance, and regulatory risk

In addition to the unique challenges of defining and evaluating explanations, organizations must also contend with more “traditional” barriers when implementing XAI. These include human resource constraints, limited computational capabilities, managerial and governance pitfalls, and legal and liability risks. However, it should be noted that such challenges are rarely examined explicitly within the narrow context of XAI. Consequently, much of the analysis in this chapter draws by analogy from the broader literature on AI transformation.

4.2.1 Human resources constraints

It is a well-known fact that data scientists are among the most sought-after professionals in today’s digital economy. This intense competition for talent drives up recruitment challenges and results in substantial hiring costs for organizations. According to a *People in AI* blog post from 2025, entry-level data scientists cost approximately \$80,190 per year, mid-level professionals average around \$99,453, while senior-level experts command salaries of about \$117,345 annually [128]. When it comes to hiring data scientists specialized in XAI, it can be expected that compensation is even more competitive. The reason for this expectation is that *XAI talent is even more niche than general data science talent* [119]. In addition to the challenges related to recruiting and paying data scientists, cross-disciplinary teams are needed to develop human-friendly and context-relevant XAI interfaces [125]. It can be expected that this will further boost the expenses of companies implementing XAI projects.

Not all human resource challenges are related to recruitment or compensation. One issue is fostering effective communication among the various roles involved. For example, one study by the RAND Corporation [129] notes that domain experts are often reluctant to engage in AI initiatives. This challenge may persist in the context of XAI, where their involvement is even more critical. Another study by Muralikumar et al. [130] identifies several difficulties in the collaboration between AI experts and user experience (UX) designers. These include a lack of fluency in AI concepts, which leads to communication breakdowns; the late involvement in the development process; and ambiguity around who is responsible for designing explanations, owning explainability, and managing user trust. Additionally, there is often a lack of organizational support, tools, and documentation to facilitate effective cross-functional collaboration between different roles.

One key challenge lies at the intersection of human resources and the hurdles for developing white-box models that can match the accuracy of black-box models, covered in Chapter 3.1.3. It can be expected that those challenges translate into costs of time and money. As Interviewee 2 noted, when asked why black-box models are preferred, he replied, “*it is cheaper.*”

The literature contains very few recommendations on how to address these challenges within the narrow context of XAI, but analogies drawn from the broader AI transformation literature can be used. Here is a list of recommendations:

- It is necessary to determine all the relevant roles, including the needed competences, education and training [92], [130].
- Recruiting graduates straight out of school and training them on explainable AI internally [119], [109].
- Hiring external talent is an obvious choice, but it is a limited option for most organizations because of labor market shortages and performance uncertainty [131].
- Contracting of third parties provides rapid access to skills through freelancers or agencies but raises concerns about cultural fit and information security [131].
- Partnering up with think tanks, universities, and research institutions, or joining industry-specific organizations that develop standard guidelines [119], [131].
- Setting up innovation labs and collaborative workshops that will give employees hands-on experience with XAI tools and allow cross-functional teams to work on XAI projects, generate ideas, and learn from one another [132], [130], also noted by Interviewee 2.
- Establishing regular question and answer sessions, internal training, and documentation to boost basic understanding of AI and streamline vocabulary [130].
- Retraining existing employees to build key capabilities and skills, especially by incentivizing traditional structured learning paths, and by using global learning platforms [132], [131].
- Fostering the development of “AI-savvy humanists” that bridge the divide between engineers and users, who may lack technical skills but still require AI understanding [125].

4.2.2 Computational capabilities constraints

It is widely known that AI in general presents a serious problem for computing capacity and costs for organizations [129]. The same concerns are relevant for XAI, as computing

explainability techniques is positively correlated with the model's complexity [119]. In some instances, the resource and time requirements may become not just burdensome but outright prohibitive [133]. Expenses go beyond hardware investments in cloud fees, but also encompass energy consumption and carbon footprint [134].

As the experiment and literature review show in Subchapter 3.2, there is a trade-off between the reliability of XAI and computational demand. The trade-offs are not limited to the choice of an XAI technique but also exist between different implementations of the same technique. This diversity is not inherently problematic. On the contrary, it enables organizations to strategically balance accuracy, interpretability, and scalability according to their operational constraints and the criticality of the use case.

Again, the literature does not provide clear guidelines for addressing the computational challenges in the narrow context of XAI. However, based on the experiment's observations, this thesis proposes three main recommendations specific to XAI:

- Using inherently interpretable models bypasses the computational challenges that are related to post-hoc explainers, with the caveat that the training of some white box models may be computationally demanding, as noted in Section 3.1.3.
- Preprocess data appropriately to drop features that are not informative [134]. If the model does not utilize a feature to generate outputs, the XAI technique will still consume computational capacity when producing explanations.
- Developing capabilities and guidelines for experimenting with the *reliability-speed trade-off* to find the optimal spot between reliability and efficiency.
- Follow the development of the nascent literature on hardware acceleration for XAI. For example, Pan and Mishra [135] propose a hardware-accelerated approach specialized for XAI, deriving explanations up to 39 times faster and 69 times more energy-efficient.

4.2.3 Managerial and governance challenges

There are ongoing efforts to establish standards, governance frameworks, and procedures to ensure the ethical and transparent use of AI in general. Some general practices and recommendations for improving governance can be applied to XAI by analogy:

- Identify key resources that are important for each stage in the AI life cycle, including data resources, tooling resources, computing resources, and human resources [92].

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- As per Subchapter 2.3, establish detailed guidelines for selecting an appropriate level of interoperability or explainability, based on the system's risk level, regulatory obligations, and the need for user trust and accountability.
 - Avoid rigidly applying traditional software development processes to AI projects, as their experimental nature requires flexibility. Instead, prioritize frequent and transparent communication with stakeholders to build trust and ensure project alignment [129].
 - As discussed in Subchapter 4.1, stakeholder involvement is essential at every stage of developing artifacts. Accordingly, it is crucial to establish policies that promote the early participation of domain experts to ensure contextual relevance and reliability, as well as their continued engagement to support the ongoing refinement of explanation artefacts.
 - As ISO/IEC 42001 [92], commitments must be included in the AI policy. Related to this is defining what constitutes success in an XAI project [130]. Accordingly, the policy should explicitly state a commitment to using interpretable models whenever feasible and, where post-hoc explainability techniques are employed, ensure they are applied in a manner that meets the specific needs of the context and stakeholders, while always striving for the most efficient implementation.
 - As per ISO/IEC 42001 [92], recommend performing impact assessment on AI Systems in planned intervals, including testing explanation artefacts in such assessments.
 - As testing is crucial to detect weakness of explanation artefacts, as discussed in Section 4.1.5, establish guidelines for testing in real-world environments with diverse stakeholder groups.
 - Focus AI projects on solving real business problems, not on using the latest technologies for their own sake [129]. This can help avoid advanced, but opaque AI models, just for the sake of following trends.

4.2.4 Legal and liability risks

While the AI Act establishes a comprehensive regulatory framework for the development and deployment of AI systems, it leaves considerable uncertainty in its practical application. The industry has criticized the AI Act for failing to consider the concept of legal certainty [3]. As Chapter 2 shows, this uncertainty extends to the explainability standards under the AI Act. This uncertainty is further exacerbated by the lack of detailed guidance in both theory and standards on what XAI technique is appropriate for which use cases (Section 4.1.1) and what constitutes

a good explanation (Subchapter 4.1). Finally, additional tension is added by the fact that organizations face sanctions of up to 3% of their annual turnover or up to €15 million, whichever is higher, in cases of breach of the explainability obligations (Section 2.1.5).

Since concrete approaches to mitigating legal risks and liability in the context of XAI and the AI Act remain limited, some of the measures proposed below are based on the author's own experience with similarly open-ended regulatory frameworks, such as the GDPR. In the absence of detailed guidance, organizations have adopted or may consider adopting one or more of the following strategies:

- Prepare a comprehensive risk assessment that will take into account the domain and context of the application, in which risks of misleading or wrong explanations will be treated, especially when such risks involve vulnerable groups like children, the elderly, marginal groups, etc. [92].
- Develop mechanisms to notice and correct nonconformity [92] potentially by ensuring efficient reporting channels.
- Maintain open communication with regulators to foster a collaborative compliance culture.
- Consider corporate structuring that ring-fences AI units, isolating them from the core business to limit exposure to legal and reputational risks. Caution is warranted, as courts may, in some instances, “pierce the corporate veil” and hold the parent entity liable.
- Leverage standards and certifications to show good-faith compliance.
- Thoroughly document and justify all decisions.
- Monitor evolving interpretations of the AI Act and adapt proactively.
- Join sectoral initiatives to gain early insights, share compliance efforts, and align industry practices.

5 The strategic context: The competitiveness and innovation trade-offs

The discussion of the AI Act's impacts on competitiveness and innovation touches on the fundamentals of various regulatory ideologies, factors driving innovation, the socio-political nature of the EU, and whether there are different expectations regarding explainability in other jurisdictions.

According to Bradford [66], many scholars and policymakers take the position that regulation inherently hinders innovation. While he acknowledges that regulatory burdens divert research and development resources to settle “compliance costs”, he also notes that regulation can be beneficial and even catalyze innovation. He notes that this catalysis can contribute to social innovations that enhance well-being, such as protecting the environment or promoting personal autonomy, as well as market innovations that boost productivity and profits, which can even create opportunities for new entrants to offer their innovative products.

There are indeed fears that the AI Act’s transparency obligations will negatively impact innovativeness and competitiveness, which will affect small and medium-sized enterprises [73]. Chapter 4 shows that organizations will face diverse challenges when implementing the explainability standards of the AI Act. Namely, compliance costs involve not only legal expenses but also the costs of hiring and training data scientists and computer interface designers, consulting domain experts, and computation-related expenses, such as the purchase of hardware or cloud services. However, the measures included in the AI Act that aim to dampen adverse effects on competitiveness and innovations should also be mentioned. Namely, the AI Act takes a proportional risk-based stance for achieving its objectives, establishes regulatory sandboxes, and allows for co-regulation by including standard-setting organizations [136].

But even though the EU is so far the only jurisdiction that has binding rules on transparency and explainability, as shown by Subchapter 2.2 virtually every ethical code, standard, and many laws or bills contain the explicit expectation that black box AI systems with significant impacts must be elucidated through the use of explainability. In addition, Subchapter 1.3 demonstrates that explainability is crucial for the adoption of AI technologies and that both the public and individuals will be reluctant to use AI tools without understanding them and their decisions. These standards and market expectations create the need for investments in XAI even without the existence of mandatory regulations. Namely, the market for XAI was already \$6.68 billion in 2023, with expectations to grow almost fivefold to \$30 billion by 2030 [137]. These investments are driven primarily by US big tech [137], [138] and start-ups [139], whose domestic jurisdiction operates in complete absence or even future expectation of AI regulations, as shown by Section 2.2.2. As a result, this thesis takes the position that the costs of compliance with explainability obligations will have a limited negative impact on the innovativeness and

competitiveness of EU organizations, because *such investments would still be necessary to offer competitive AI products even in the absence of a regulation.*

But the lack of typical regulation in other jurisdictions might not persist in the long run. Some organizations may fall under the *Brussels Effect*, which manifests itself along the following two dimensions [56]: **i) the political dimension**, as third countries align their legislation with the AI Act to maintain trade ties; and **ii) the practical dimension**, as foreign companies adopt the AI Act's standards as the highest one to avoid creating separate product lines for different jurisdictions. If the Brussels Effect takes hold, then the divergence in explainability standards between the EU and other jurisdictions will be further reduced.

When discussing the impact of the AI Act, it is also essential to consider the socio-political circumstances in the EU. Before even proposing the AI Act, a public consultation by the Parliament's Committee on Legal Affairs [140] revealed that 90% of stakeholders supported the regulation of AI. In the context of such demand for AI regulation and the political nature of the EU, the alternative to the AI Act would not have been a *laissez-faire* regulatory landscape like in the US, but rather a complex web of member state rules [66]. In such a scenario, organizations would have faced compliance costs for 27 jurisdictions instead of one. To counter such tendencies, the AI Act takes what Veale et al. [141] call the maximum harmonization approach, which limits the Member States' ability to legislate independently in this area. They give a notable caveat, though, since previous experiences, like with the GDPR, show that it takes a significant amount of time before divergent interpretations of member states are streamlined [136]. None of this is to say that the explainability standards are an unavoidable byproduct of the calls for regulation and maximum harmonization. Still, it can be speculated that even with such high standards, the AI Act is a more desirable alternative than a fragmented regulatory landscape.

The biggest downside of the AI Act is that it undoubtedly creates significant legal uncertainty. Meyers [136] notes that this is especially bad in the field of AI: **i)** where organizations must invest vast amounts of capital in projects that will be unprofitable for a significant time and therefore long-term legal certainty is essential; and **ii)** where significant technical and commercial experimentation is necessary. As Section 2.1.4 showed, there are conflicting views on whether explainability is even necessary. At the same time, delays in producing the harmonized standards of the ESOs, as presented in Section 2.1.1, coupled with the overall difficulties in defining and evaluating the explanations noted in Subchapter 4.1, create legal

uncertainty for organizations trying to comply with the AI Act. The experience with the GDPR teaches us that authorities in the member states will have different interpretations of the AI Act's provisions [136]. The potential for such divergent interpretations is increased because, by default, multiple institutions in member states will implement the AI Act, as outlined in Section 2.1.5. Another source of uncertainty noted by Meyers is the Commission's power to issue delegated acts to expand the list of systems considered high risk under Annex III. This creates the risk that an organization may invest years in developing an AI product that is initially not classified as high-risk and not subject to explainability requirements, only for the Commission later to expand the Annex III list via a delegated act, retroactively subjecting the product to explainability obligations and potentially undermining the viability of the entire business model.

Finally, maybe too much weight is being given to the EU's regulatory approach when exploring Europe's lagging behind the USA in terms of innovativeness, competitiveness, and technology adoption [142], [66], [73]. Bradford [66] states that there are more fundamental forces that determine the EU's underperformance, such as: **i) absence of a digital single market** resulting from linguistic, consumer taste, purchase power and regulatory divergence among member states; **ii) absence of deep and integrated capital markets** resulting from the absence native venture capital and comparative low state financing; **iii) stringent bankruptcy laws and risk averse culture**; **iv) absence of coherent immigration policy** to attract talent and a concurrent brain drain from EU to the US.

6 Framework for implementing explainability

This final chapter presents the key result of this thesis: a *structured framework to guide AI providers in developing and deploying high-risk AI systems in compliance with the explainability requirements of the EU AI Act*, with particular emphasis on Articles 13 and 14. The framework is grounded in the findings of the preceding chapters: **i)** Chapter 2 which examined the legal and ethical dimensions of explainability and defined the relevant regulatory standards; **ii)** Chapter 3, which surveyed some of the available methods and tools for meeting those standards; and **iii)** Chapter 4, which addressed the organizational challenges involved in implementing explainability, with a particular focus on designing usable explanation artefacts, managing reliability–computational trade-offs, and mitigating legal risks.

Turning to the framework itself, it is organized into six distinct phases, each comprising three actionable steps. For better clarity and usability, the framework is presented in a tabular format that outlines the objectives and activities of each phase. In addition, the framework is visualized in Figure 30 to provide an intuitive overview of the sequential and iterative nature of the process.

Table 1. Framework for implementing explainability in high-risk AI Systems

PHASE 1 ESTABLISH APPLICABILITY	
Step I:	Determine whether the planned AI System would meet the definition of AI under the AI Act. Key criteria and details are discussed in 2.1.2.1.
Step II:	Check if the planned system falls into one of the several categories of systems that are excluded from the AI Act's scope (e.g., military, defense, or national security purposes).
Step III:	<p>Determine whether the planned system falls into the category of a high-risk system under the AI Act. This should be done depending on the nature of the system by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • examining if the system would be subject to a third-party conformity assessment if it represents a product or safety component of a product that falls under the harmonization legislation listed in Annex I; • if the intended use of the system is covered by the use cases listed in Annex III, if the system touches on the eight sensitive areas of Annex III. In this case, it should be examined whether any exceptions are applicable, such as when the AI System is intended to perform a narrow procedural task or improve the result of a previously completed human activity. <p>See more details in 2.1.3.</p>
PHASE 2 MAPPING OF EXPLANATION NEEDS AND STAKEHOLDERS	
Step I:	Stakeholders should be mapped according to the context in which the AI system will operate. This mapping must aim to reflect the actual diversity of individuals who will interact with the system by considering the users' varied cultural backgrounds, professional experience, technical proficiencies, and domain-specific expertise.
Step II:	By consulting domain experts, industry publications, and market surveillance authorities, determine the appropriate level of reliability of explanations based on the framework introduced in 2.3. This framework distinguishes between three categories of explainability requirements: i) mandatory interpretability use cases; ii) strict explainability use cases; and iii) balanced explainability use cases. If the use case requires strict interpretability, proceed with an interpretable model directly to Phase 4.

Step III:	Test if the intended purpose and other responsible AI standards (accuracy, robustness, security) can be achieved with a white box. If the results are positive, proceed directly to Phase 4 with an interpretable model. Otherwise, if the results are negative and the intended purpose allows for balancing other values against explainability, proceed with a black box model.
Note:	To avoid confusion, it should be clarified that regardless of whether an interpretable or explainable model is used, the next step involves developing such a model. This framework deliberately omits the model development phase, as its primary focus is on understanding and evaluating AI model decisions in light of the explainability obligations under the AI Act, rather than on how the models themselves are built.
PHASE 3: TECHNICAL DESIGN OF XAI SOLUTION	
Step I:	If the system is based on a black-box model, select the appropriate XAI techniques through a multidisciplinary team comprising data scientists, compliance officers, and domain experts. The use of the plural in “techniques” is deliberate: even for a single AI system, multiple XAI techniques may be employed, either to serve the needs of different stakeholder roles or to provide complementary perspectives on the same task. Combining local and global explanation methods, as well as visual and rule-based formats, can provide a more comprehensive understanding of model behavior. If possible, consult the market surveillance authority to determine whether the chosen XAI technique meets standards.
Step II:	Optimize the implementation of selected XAI techniques to strike a balance between computational efficiency and explanation reliability. Different implementations of the same technique can produce markedly different results in terms of both speed and stability. The optimal point should be established based on the particular use case, resource constraints, and available computational infrastructure. For inspiration, read Subsection 3.2.3.2.
Step III:	Test the technical reliability of the implemented XAI. Use the benchmarks listed in 3.2.1. Return to Step I or Step II if reliability is not satisfactory.
PHASE 4: DEVELOPING AND TESTING EXPLANATION ARTEFACTS	
Step I:	Identify the format, style, and level of detail suitable for each user group, based on the diverse needs of different stakeholders. Read Section 4.1.3 for structured classification of stakeholders. Design decisions should be informed by the earlier stakeholder mapping exercise (Phase 2) and guided by principles such as contrastivity, selectivity, and social context. Stakeholders should be included from the very start of this phase, not as test subjects, but as equal co-designers, as suggested by Section 4.1.5.
Step II:	Integrate usability testing into the development process. This includes both qualitative feedback from representative users and an empirical evaluation of the quality of explanations. The benchmark for human-friendly explanations

	discussed in Section 4.1.2 can be used to assess the comprehensibility and actionability of explanations.
Step III:	Proactively test for unwanted outcomes, such as automation bias, overreliance, or a misunderstanding of explanations. This involves evaluating whether users develop unjustified trust in the system, fail to question its outputs, or misinterpret the scope and reliability of the provided explanations. Particular attention should be paid to how different user groups interact with explanation artefacts. To guard against this, explanation interfaces should communicate their limitations and boundaries of validity to mitigate false impressions of transparency. See more in Section 4.1.5.
Note:	While the steps covered in this phase are designed to be followed in sequence, they are also iterative in nature. Each step should inform and refine the others through repeated feedback loops, ensuring continuous improvement of explanation design and usability.
PHASE 5: DEPLOYMENT PREPARATION	
Step I:	Before placing the system on the market, the explanation-related artefacts must be documented in the relevant compliance materials. This primarily includes the: i) instructions for use as required under Article 13 paragraph 3 of the AI Act; ii) risk assessment as required by Article 9 of the AI Act; and iii) technical documentation as required by Article 11 of the AI Act. For details on what should be included in each point of the compliance documentation listed above, refer to Section 2.1.4.
Step II:	The system must undergo the necessary <i>ex ante conformity</i> steps. Firstly, the system should be aligned with harmonized standards or common specifications to benefit from the <i>presumption of conformity</i> . Depending on the system's risk profile and classification, this assessment may be carried out internally or require evaluation by a notified body. As a final step, an <i>EU Declaration of Conformity</i> must be issued, after which the system can bear the <i>CE marking</i> and be placed on the market. Some AI Systems covered by Annex III should also be registered under Article 49, paragraph 1 of the AI Act. For more details, refer to Section 2.1.5.
Step III:	A post-market monitoring and continuous improvement plan should be put in place before launch to ensure that explanation mechanisms remain effective, reliable, and responsive to evolving user needs and regulatory expectations. This plan should include logging user interactions with explanation interfaces, collecting structured feedback on usability and comprehension, and monitoring incidents where explanations were misunderstood, ignored, or caused concern. Periodic audits or internal reviews should assess whether explanation artefacts continue to meet quality and relevance standards. To support these activities, responsibility for explainability oversight should be assigned to a dedicated lead or team, and escalation procedures should be in place for unresolved issues.

PHASE 6:	
Step I:	Provide training to deployers of the AI system, ensuring they understand the system's functionality, the purpose and limitations of its explanation mechanisms, and their responsibilities under the AI Act. This step is a continuous and ongoing process from deployment to retirement.
Step II:	Utilize mechanisms from Phase 5, Step III to gather information, monitor usage, and communicate with relevant stakeholders, thereby preparing to enhance the efficiency, reliability, and usefulness of explanation techniques and interfaces in future updates, as well as policies, and processes.
Step III:	Based on inputs from Step II, as well as on advancements in available technologies, organizational know-how, and regulatory guidance, organizations should continuously improve the efficiency, reliability, and usability of explanation systems. In addition to enhancing the AI System itself, improve policies and processes.

Before concluding this chapter and proceeding to the final discussions, it should be emphasized that this framework has a narrow focus: it addresses only the explainability dimension of compliance, rather than the full lifecycle of AI development or the complete conformity process under the AI Act. Its purpose is to be integrated into and enhance broader AI governance policies, risk management frameworks, and AI System design processes. The framework consolidates findings from this thesis that are directly relevant to the development of AI systems in line with the explainability standards of the AI Act. It does not aim to deal with the additional challenges that may limit an organization's capacity to apply this framework or to meet the AI Act's requirements, even though they were covered in Subchapter 4.2. For guidance on strategies to boost organizational capacity, readers are advised to consult the recommendations provided in that chapter.

Figure 30. The Framework for implementing explainability in high-risk AI Systems under the AI Act

7 Conclusion

This thesis largely achieved its objective of developing a framework within the context of the AI Act to guide businesses in implementing explainability. It also addressed many of the key challenges and trade-offs that organizations face across the normative, technological, and organizational dimensions of complying with XAI standards.

The chapter on the legal context showed that, from the outset of the legislative process that culminated with the AI Act, EU institutions recognized the opacity of black-box systems as a risk to fundamental values and positioned explainability as essential to ethical AI. The discussion on the AI Act itself demonstrated that transparency and human oversight requirements for high-risk AI systems necessitate explanation interfaces that must rely on XAI when black-box models are used. While many ethical codes, standards, and policy books offer general principles on the topic of explainability, they lack concrete guidance on how to practically balance *the trade-off between explainability and other values of trustworthy AI*. Nonetheless, based on how explainability is treated in the covered normative acts, this thesis proposes that high-risk systems will likely fall into three informal categories: i) those requiring interpretability; ii) those needing a strict level of explainability; and iii) those allowing a more flexible trade-off. Though broad, this categorization may assist in further segmenting explainability requirements across use cases.

The chapter on the technological context identified two main technical paths to achieving explainability: i) using white-box models to ensure inherent interpretability, or ii) applying XAI methods to understand black-box models. Both paths offer a range of methods, each with distinct advantages and limitations. The white-box approach is constrained by the *accuracy-interpretability trade-off*, as even those who reject its inevitability acknowledge the difficulty of constructing competitive interpretable models. XAI methods, meanwhile, present a *trade-off between reliability and computational efficiency*. As the experiment demonstrated, some techniques were highly resource-intensive, while faster methods lacked stability. Notably, significant variation was observed not only across techniques but also between different implementations of the same method.

Finally, the chapter on the organizational context highlighted the novelty of implementing XAI in real-world settings. Interest in developing human-friendly AI explanations has emerged only recently, and creating usable, safe explanation interfaces often proves more challenging than

building the models themselves. This is because developing such interfaces requires integrating knowledge and fostering collaboration across diverse domains, such as data science, domain expertise, compliance, end-user experience, and human-computer interaction. The lack of common experiences, methodologies, and shared vocabulary further exacerbates this challenge. Still, the chapter identified several actionable resources to support the design and testing of explanation artifacts. The most underdefined challenges lie in resource constraints, governance, and legal risk management, areas in which this thesis has relied on analogies from the broader AI field.

To conclude, it is worth addressing the explainability in a context that is currently in the focus of policymakers, business leaders, and the public: the AI Act's impact on competitiveness and innovation. While concerns about the AI Act's broader obligations may be justified, its explainability requirements are unlikely to exert a negative influence on competitiveness and innovation on their own. Most global AI standards and ethical codes already demand explainability, and the Brussels Effect suggests that EU standards will influence practices beyond its borders. Moreover, market demand for explainable AI is rising sharply, with projections showing a fivefold increase between 2023 and 2030. In this light, explainability is better viewed as a source of competitive advantage than a constraint. Ultimately, the EU's competitiveness will be shaped less by regulation and more by structural challenges such as market fragmentation, legal uncertainty, limited venture capital, and talent outflows.

To further support compliance and the implementation of XAI, future research should develop practical guidelines for managing the trade-offs discussed in this thesis, with a focus on specific industries, segmentation of use cases, identification of suitable XAI techniques for particular applications, and definition of key elements for explanation interfaces tailored to those contexts.

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Appendix 1 – Questions for semi structured interview

Part I: General questions

1. Tell me more about your AI/ML related activities?
2. Does your organization use inherently interpretable models, or do you rely more on black-box systems?
3. Do you include third-party models/systems in your systems? Are they interpretable or black box models? How do you assess their reliability and regulatory fitness, especially in terms of understanding them and their decisions?
4. Is interpretability/explainability important for your company? If yes, do you see it as a legal compliance requirement or a business enabler (e.g. trust, adoption, customer relations)?
5. How would you define “explainability” in your organization, and do you distinguish it from related concepts like interpretability or transparency?
6. Do your customers have any demand regarding the interpretability/explainability of the model?

Part II: Questions about the experiences and challenges when implementing XAI

7. What types of XAI techniques (e.g., SHAP, LIME, PDP, surrogate models) have your organization used or experimented with?
8. What technical challenges have you faced when implementing explainability solutions in your systems (e.g., computational costs, stability of explanations, integration)? How do you solve them?
9. What internal challenges do you face when operating explainability (e.g., lack of skills, unclear ownership, cross-department misalignment)? How do you solve them?
10. Who is typically involved in selecting and implementing explainability techniques – data scientists, compliance officers, and domain experts?
11. Are you planning or implementing tools or interfaces to allow deployers (end users) to interpret and challenge model decisions?
12. Do you measure or guard against the risks of automation bias, misinterpretation, or other dangers on the side of the recipient of explanations?
13. Has your organization established internal standards or workflows to guide explainability efforts across different AI projects?
14. Have you had any related experiences about building interpretable models – costs, challenge, HR issues?

Part IV: Questions about the ethical and legal aspects

15. Are there specific use cases where explainability is more important or even essential in your business operations?
16. Are there specific scenarios where interpretability is preferred over explainability, and are there different grades of explainability?
17. Have you encountered concerns about legal or reputational risks related to opacity in AI decisions?
18. Do you think end users (e.g. clinicians, risk officers, customers) make use of the explanations provided?

Part IV: Questions about the ethical and legal aspects

19. What changes (technical, legal, organizational) would help you implement explainability more effectively in your systems?
20. Do you think the AI Act will drive innovation in explainable AI or create more barriers to AI deployment?
21. In your view, is the explainability requirement in the AI Act proportional to the actual risks posed by AI in your sector?
22. What would a practical, business-friendly framework for explainability look like to you? What elements would it need to include?